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D6 Calibration and measurement procedures of X-ray multimeters at laboratories and clinical conditions covering relevant clinical parameters such as air kerma, PPV and half-value layer and target uncertainties submitted to IAEA CRP E24024 officers providing inputs for the update of the TRS-457

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VINS

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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1 Summary

This deliverable contains recommendations for calibration and measurement procedures for X-ray multimeters (XMM) that can be used by radiation metrologists and clinical medical physicists in laboratory and clinical conditions. Section 2 gives general guidance for calibration of XMMs. Sections 3 to 5 describe calibration procedures in laboratory conditions in terms of air kerma, tube voltage and half-value layer (HVL), which are developed in such way to be easy to implement at the Secondary Standards Dosimetry Laboratory (SSDL) level. Section 6 discusses other quantities that are measured by the XMMs. Sections 7 to 9 describe calibration and measurement procedures adapted for the use with clinical X-ray machines. Section 10 gives guidance for uncertainty estimation for clinical measurements. Finally, section 11 gives list of references for further reading.

A draft version of this deliverable has been presented and discussed at the 3rd RCM meeting of the IAEA CRP E24024 (Fig. 1.1). Final version of the deliverable was submitted to the officers of the IAEA CRP E24024 officers providing inputs for the update of the TRS-457 (Fig 1.2).

Figure 1.1 D6 draft and related topics were discussed in the CRP meeting October 2025 at the IAEA.

TraMeXI Deliverable 6 for IAEA CRP E24024

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pe 22.5.2026 14.21

Dear Zakithi and Olivera,

I would like to share with you another TraMeXI deliverable: Deliverable 6 "Calibration and measurement procedures of X-ray multimeters at laboratories and clinical conditions covering relevant clinical parameters such as air kerma, PPV and half-value layer and target uncertainties submitted to IAEA CRP E24024 officers providing inputs for the update of the TRS-457".

This deliverable, which provides input for the update of TRS-457, was already discussed during the last CRP meeting in October 2025. It has now been updated to reflect the discussions and comments received at that meeting. I hope you find it useful, and I would be happy to discuss it further if needed.

Following this email, we will submit the deliverable to EURAMET for approval. If needed, we will provide you with the final approved version at a later stage.

Best regards,
Paula

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Figure 1.2 Proof of email with D6 sent to the IAEA CRP officers 22nd May 2026

2 Special considerations for calibration laboratories

2.1 General guidance

Ionization chambers have traditionally served as the reference instruments for dosimetry in diagnostic X-ray imaging. In recent years, XMMs have become increasingly common in clinical and quality assurance applications (Komatina et al., 2025). Unlike ionization chambers, XMMs are typically multi-element instruments capable of measuring different parameters in a single exposure. The reported values are derived through internal algorithms that combine detector signals with software-based corrections.

The fundamental measurement principles, detector geometry, energy and angular response, and data processing of XMMs can differ substantially from those of ionization chambers. In addition, XMMs often provide quantities that are not directly traceable to traditional dosimetric methods without additional assumptions or corrections. As a consequence, general calibration guidance developed primarily for ionization chambers does not always adequately address the specific characteristics and limitations of XMMs.

In particular, the use of internal calibration factors, restricted access to raw detector signals, software-dependent measurement modes, and automatic radiation-quality-based corrections introduce challenges that are not encountered with conventional dosimetry systems. These aspects necessitate additional care in defining calibration conditions, documenting instrument settings, and communicating results to end users.

Therefore, there is a need to supplement existing codes of practice with guidance specifically addressing the calibration and testing of XMMs. However, the following sub-sections outline terminology and special considerations intended to support calibration laboratories in achieving traceable, transparent, and reproducible calibrations for these instruments. Sometimes the XMM concept is not clear, and the sub-chapters below provide information on special considerations.

2.2 Note on the use of the word XMM

In this document, the term XMM also includes instruments that can measure tube voltage non-invasively, but do not measure other quantities. Some semiconductor detectors work on a simpler principle: e.g. they are used with regular electrometers, use a single calibration coefficient over the whole range, can provide raw signal or cannot measure parameters other than air kerma. It is a matter of definition if such detectors are considered XMMs, but their calibration is usually simpler. The following discussion is mostly relevant for multi-element and multi-quantity XMMs, and some of the problems might not be directly applicable for these single-element or single-quantity XMMs.

2.3 Special considerations for XMM calibration

Many XMMs use multi-element semi-conductor detectors positioned behind different filters. The measured value is calculated based on the signals from each detector and the ratios of the signals. In most cases, the calibration laboratory and the end-user do not have access to the XMM calibration function or algorithm, so the XMM functions effectively as a black box. One of the consequences is that the raw signal in most cases can't be obtained by the calibration laboratory.

Many XMMs use software with many different selections that can be made by the user, such as the tube HV, total filtration, modality, anode material or other. In many cases, the selections significantly influence the end results, because either the calibration coefficient or the calibration function changes. Therefore, in case of these XMMs, it is very important to specify all relevant software settings in the calibration certificate, as well as the software name and version.

Most XMMs perform automatic corrections of air kerma value and some other quantity values based on the measured radiation quality (i.e. parameters related to radiation quality are automatically determined and a correction is performed) or other conditions. Considering that the calibration laboratory and user do not have access to calibration functions and algorithms, it is often not clear in which way the calibration conditions influence the corrections. It is also not clear if there may be discontinuities in the calibration functions. Because of this, it is very important to specify calibration conditions in the calibration certificate.

Some software packages used with XMMs are very complicated and they require some level of training. Some software packages allow the user to select special measurement modes or parameters that may influence the measurement result. It is therefore important to communicate with the user about the way that the specific XMM is used. In some cases, it can be beneficial to invite the user to attend the calibration and control the software.

XMM indications of air kerma are not corrected for air density, as opposed to the ionization chambers. If the correction is erroneously applied, the error that is introduced can be several percent or even more.

Most XMMs are covered with shielding from the back and the sides and their viewing angle is very different from ionization chambers. This is why the XMMs are very sensitive to the angle of incidence, as opposed to ionization chambers. It should be carefully checked that the beam axis is perpendicular to the XMM entrance surface. XMMs can also be sensitive to the orientation with respect to the anode-cathode direction, because of the anode heel effect and the fact that the dose is a function of the ratio of the signals measured by different detector elements. If the radiation field is not sufficiently homogenous, failing to properly orient the detector can significantly influence the result. Because of this, the dosimeters should be oriented as per manufacturer instructions, and the orientation should be stated in the calibration certificate.

In addition, the XMMs see scattered radiation differently compared to ionization chambers and this should be considered if there is a large scattering component in the X-ray beam used for calibration. Under calibration conditions, this effect is usually negligible.

2.4 Special notes for establishing radiation qualities

A range of radiation qualities is typically applied when X-ray imaging dosimeters are calibrated. A standardized set of reference radiation qualities is typically used for calibration of ionization chambers. End-users can use the ionization chambers for a clinical range of radiation qualities using HVL interpolation. However, for XMMs these interpolations are not recommended (Toroi et al., 2026).

Radiation quality is typically established based on the tube voltage, added filtration and measured HVL. All the items used in the beam during the calibration should be considered when the radiation quality is established. For example, if a monitor chamber is used, it should be in the beam (even if it is switched off) during all measurements and calibrations, as well as for radiation quality validation. If monitor chamber is not consistently in the beam, differences in air kerma output and radiation quality will occur, especially for the lower photon energies.

It is recommended to use high voltage (HV) dividers during calibrations. HV dividers help to maintain standard values of tube voltage throughout calibrations. If it is not possible to have a HV divider connected at all times, it is recommended to use it at least during the validation of radiation qualities. Spectrometry capabilities are not mandatory for SSDs. However, spectrometry can be used to validate radiation qualities, by calculating parameters related to X-ray spectra (HVL, homogeneity, mean energy). Spectrum end point is related to the maximum peak tube voltage (kV_p). Measuring the spectrum end point is especially useful if HV divider is not available. Some laboratories use alternate method – HV measurements using XMMs. If this method is used, traceability in terms of practical peak voltage (PPV) should be established for each radiation quality and measurement uncertainty should be considered. For constant potential HV generators, kV_p and PPV are practically equal. It should be noted that the accuracy requirements for tube voltage measurements can be different when the values are used as reference values for calibration compared to just using them to establish radiation qualities.

3 Calibration of XMMs in terms of air kerma

3.1 Scope and general considerations

This section deals with calibration and testing of dosimeters used for diagnostic and interventional radiology in terms of air kerma and air kerma rate. Even though the procedure is written with XMMs in mind, general principles are also applicable to calibrations of ionization chambers.

A reference class ionization chamber is used to establish traceability to a Primary Standards Dosimetry Laboratory (PSDL), and it is recommended to calibrate the chamber for all radiation qualities that are established and used in the SSDL. If this is not possible, the range of radiation qualities should at least cover the range of radiation qualities (characterized by HVL) that are used in the laboratory. If the calibration coefficient for reference instrument is determined by interpolation between calibration coefficients for other radiation qualities, additional uncertainty due to interpolation should be considered. Extrapolation of calibration coefficients is not recommended.

3.2 Geometry and positioning

It is common to use the distance of 1 m for calibrations of dosimeters used in diagnostic and interventional radiology. In some cases, a shorter distance of e.g. 60 cm is used for mammography dosimeter calibrations. Calibration certificate of the secondary standard should be consulted when choosing the irradiation distance. If a different distance is used, this should be considered during the uncertainty analysis.

All irradiations are performed free-in-air. Any support that is used should be made of low-Z material to reduce the contribution of scattered radiation.

The field size should be sufficient to uniformly irradiate different types of reference dosimeters and user dosimeters. However, the field size should be as small as feasible, to reduce the contribution of scattered radiation. Field size should be the same for measurement with reference dosimeter and user dosimeter, to avoid differences in scatter conditions. Nominal field size of 10 cm x 10 cm, or circular field with the radius of 10 cm is suitable for most calibrations.

Dosimeters are positioned in the reference orientation and with the reference point positioned at the point of test. The reference point can be found in the dosimeter documentation (e.g. user manual or technical specification provided by the manufacturer), and it is often marked on the dosimeters. Deviations from the reference orientation are usually insignificant for spherical and cylindrical ionization chambers (at the level of uncertainty typical for SSDLs). However, even small deviations may be significant for plane parallel chambers.

3.3 Calibration procedure

There are three basic possibilities for calibration procedures for dosimeter calibrations:

1. Calibration by substitution
2. Calibration by substitution with a monitor chamber
3. Calibration using a calibrated monitor chamber

In the following sections, the explanations are based on charge measurements. However, current measurements can be performed instead, and the procedures otherwise remain unchanged.

3.3.1 Calibration by substitution

Calibration by substitution can be used when the stability of the X-ray tube is expected to be very high during the measurements needed for the calibration (e.g. several hours with multiple exposures), and especially in cases when the short-term stability of the X-ray tube is expected to be better than the stability of the monitor chamber.

Calibration by substitution means that the reference chamber and user instrument are positioned in the radiation field sequentially, at the same point of test. The measurements are done in two exposures. First the reference value is measured using a reference chamber, and then the user instrument is irradiated and its indication is recorded. The calibration coefficient is calculated according to the equation (3.1):

$$N_K = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}} N_{K,\text{ref}} \prod k_{\text{ref},i}}{M \prod k_{u,i}} \quad (3.1)$$

where N_K and $N_{K,\text{ref}}$ are calibration coefficients of the user and reference instrument respectively, Q_{ref} is the charge collected by reference measurement chain, M is the indication of the user instrument (it can be charge, or dose, or some related quantity) and $k_{u,i}$ and $k_{\text{ref},i}$ are correction factors for user and reference instrument. Most commonly used corrections are for air density (k_d) and radiation quality (k_Q). Other corrections are usually not applied. However, many of them are included implicitly, in such way that they are considered to be equal to 1, and uncertainty is estimated for these correction factors. Examples are correction for distance from the X-ray tube focus, reference measurement chain stability and non-linearity, field non-uniformity and irradiation time.

Background indication of the XMMs is in many cases 0 or very close to 0. Many XMMs are triggered by radiation, and background indication therefore cannot be obtained. Reference chambers are typically zeroed. Residual leakage is in most cases smaller than 0.1 % of the signal and can be safely ignored. In cases when background indication is significant, it should be subtracted from the indication of the affected instrument.

Correction for air density, due to variations of air temperature and pressure, is always performed for vented chambers. Failing to perform this correction may cause significant errors. Even assuming that the room temperature is within (20 ± 2) °C, due to variations of air pressure, these errors can be typically up to several percent at altitudes close to sea level, and much higher at higher altitudes. The correction is performed according to the equation (3.2):

$$k_d = \frac{T p_0}{T_0 p} \quad (3.2)$$

where T and T_0 are the measured temperature and the reference temperature (expressed in K) respectively, and p and p_0 are the measured pressure and the reference pressure respectively. Reference conditions are usually 293.15 K (20 °C) and 1013.25 mbar. However, they can be defined differently. SSDL should make sure that the calibration coefficient of the secondary standard is expressed for the same conditions that are used for future calibrations (otherwise, the calibration coefficient should be recalculated; correction can be obtained using the equation 3.2).

Correction for radiation quality (k_Q) is applied if the reference chamber calibration coefficient is stated for a radiation quality different from the one used for calibration. The correction factors can be provided by a primary laboratory in the corresponding calibration certificate (i.e. calibration factor is given for the reference radiation quality (e.g. RQR 5), and correction factors are given for other radiation qualities) or can be obtained by interpolation, based on the known calibration coefficients for other radiation qualities and the HVLs. Extrapolation is not recommended.

An electrometer calibration coefficient may also be applied, if the electrometer is calibrated separately from the chamber. It is usually denoted as k_{elec} .

A monitor chamber can be used in calibration by substitution. In this case, the indication of the monitor chamber is not included in the calculation, it is only used to validate that there are no unexpected failures (e.g. shutter failure). Uncertainty contribution of the monitor chamber is also not included in the budget in this method, but it can be used to verify that the uncertainty component related to the long-term stability is not exceeded.

3.3.2 Calibration by substitution with a monitor chamber

Calibration by substitution with a monitor chamber is used when it is expected that the stability of the monitor chamber is better than the stability of the X-ray tube. Therefore, using the monitor chamber to normalize the indications of the reference and user instruments improves the accuracy of the calibration. This method can also be useful if the X-ray tube current and high voltage are set manually, which can cause small differences in tube output between subsequent irradiations. Finally, if the irradiation time is not the same for the reference instrument and user instrument, normalization to monitor chamber indication can be used instead of time measurement (e.g. reference measurements of 60 s are performed, and the exposures during the XMM measurement are 6 s each).

This procedure is very similar to calibration by substitution. The only difference is that the values of the reference chamber and the user instrument are normalized to monitor chamber indications. Equation (3.1) becomes equation (3.3):

$$N_K = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}} N_{K,\text{ref}} \prod k_{\text{ref},i}}{M \prod k_{u,i}} \frac{Q_{M,u} \prod k_{M,u,i}}{Q_{M,\text{ref}} \prod k_{M,\text{ref},i}} \quad (3.3)$$

where $Q_{M,u}$ and $Q_{M,\text{ref}}$ are charges collected by the monitor chamber during user instrument and reference chamber irradiations respectively. Other symbols have the same meaning as in equation (3.1). Monitor chamber indications are corrected only for air density. Differences due to dose rate, radiation quality, stability and all other influence quantities can usually be considered insignificant, because the irradiations are performed sequentially in the same nominal conditions. It is recommended to use two thermometers, one for reference chamber and one for monitor chamber. If only one thermometer is used, the correction factors for air density will cancel out (except for XMMs which do not have air density correction). In that case, an additional uncertainty component due to the difference between the temperatures in the sensitive volumes of monitor chamber and reference chamber should be considered.

3.3.3 Calibration using a calibrated monitor chamber

Calibration using a calibrated monitor chamber is advantageous when a large number of calibrations is performed, and measurement uncertainty is not of the primary importance. These calibrations can be many times faster than calibrations performed by using the aforementioned methods.

In this method, equation (3.1) is used, but a monitor chamber is used as the reference chamber. It should be noted that monitor chambers are not reference class chambers. They have much worse energy dependence than reference class chambers, and the response dependence on air pressure may be different (some monitor chambers can slightly change shape and volume with the air pressure). The uncertainty components are in principle the same as for the calibration by substitution, but some contributions are larger (see section 3.5).

Monitor chamber is always positioned in the field, so only one irradiation is performed exposing the monitor chamber and the user instrument simultaneously. It is important to note that the monitor chamber used in this manner is operating as a KAP-meter (only part of the active volume is in the beam). Because of this, monitor chamber calibration coefficient is valid only if the monitor chamber is not moved between calibrations, and if the same distance and field size are used.

3.4 Uncertainty budget

The uncertainty of calibration coefficient is calculated by applying the relevant international guides, for example JCGM GUM (JCGM, 2008). Typical uncertainties for calibration coefficients in SSDLs are between 1 % and 3 % ($k = 2$), (BIPM, 2026). Considering that the uncertainties are propagated quadratically, sources of uncertainty equal to 0.1 % account for between 0.4 % and 4 % of the combined uncertainty. Any uncertainty components smaller than 0.1 % are therefore usually safe to ignore, i.e. omitting them from the uncertainty

budget will cause insignificant underestimation of the combined uncertainty. Further guidance and examples can be found in IAEA TECDOC 1585 (IAEA, 2008).

Uncertainty analysis is specific for each laboratory. The examples and discussion presented here should be critically considered when the laboratory creates its own uncertainty budget, and they should be adapted to the equipment, procedures and experience of the specific laboratory.

3.4.1 Assumptions

It is assumed here that the reader is familiar with the basics of the uncertainty theory, such as probability distribution functions (normal, rectangular and triangular), propagation of measurement uncertainty, expanded uncertainty, coverage factors and similar concepts. In these examples, it is considered that the uncertainty contributions are either completely uncorrelated or completely correlated. For more information see (JCGM, 2008). A simpler explanation relevant for ionizing radiation calibrations is available in IAEA TECDOC 1585 (IAEA, 2008).

3.4.2 Model equation

Equation 3.3 is considered as the model equation for the purpose of this discussion and it is repeated here:

$$N_K = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}} N_{K,\text{ref}} \prod k_{\text{ref},i}}{M \prod k_{u,i}} \frac{Q_{M,u} \prod k_{M,u,i}}{Q_{M,\text{ref}} \prod k_{M,\text{ref},i}}$$

This equation has only multiplication and division (some multipliers may have powers different from 1). Propagation of uncertainty can be simplified in this special case, in such way that the following equation is valid:

$$u_c^2 = \sum c_i^2 u_i^2 \quad (3.4)$$

where u_c is the relative combined uncertainty (i.e. relative uncertainty of the calibration coefficient), c_i is the i -th sensitivity coefficient (this is equal to the power of the i -th multiplier or divider) and u_i is the relative uncertainty of the i -th multiplier (or divider). It should be noted that the square of the sensitivity coefficient is used for calculation, so the negative powers (division) influence the combined uncertainty in the same way as positive powers. In the following discussion, the sensitivity coefficients are mentioned only if they differ from 1.

3.4.3 Repeatability and resolution

Repeatability and resolution are considered for all measurement instruments that influence the calibration coefficient. In many cases, their contribution is below 0.1 % and can be ignored. These contributions are treated in the same way as for any other measurement, and are not discussed here in detail.

3.4.4 Calibration coefficient of the reference chamber (or measurement system)

Calibration coefficient of the reference chamber is stated in the corresponding calibration certificate. It is typical to assume normal distribution for this uncertainty, and to state it with coverage factor 2. The uncertainty is usually between 1 % and 2 % for secondary standards ($k = 2$). This contribution can be reduced if the secondary standard is calibrated in a primary laboratory with small measurement uncertainty (CMCs of National Measurement Institutes are given in BIPM (2026)). This contribution can also be increased if the secondary standard is not used directly for calibrations, but another reference chamber (or monitor chamber) is calibrated in comparison with the secondary standard.

The decision on which instrument to use for calibrations and where to calibrate the secondary standard is a compromise between the calibration cost, national (or regional) availability of calibration laboratories, number of calibrations performed, requirements of each separate user, risk for damaging secondary standard etc.

It is common to calibrate ionization chambers together with the electrometer. In this case, only one calibration coefficient is used for the measurement system. If the chamber is calibrated separately, the electrometer should also be calibrated. In this case, two calibration coefficients are used and each of them has separate measurement uncertainty.

3.4.5 Long-term stability of the reference chamber (or measurement system)

Long-term stability and stability are used interchangeably in this document. Short-term stability is discussed under “repeatability”. It is common to check the stability of all the ionization chambers that are used for calibrations. Stability checks should not be too frequent (there is a risk of damaging the chamber), but also not too infrequent (if a chamber fails stability check, the number of non-conforming calibrations will be higher). If a calibration laboratory performs a few calibrations (e.g. up to 50 per year), three months is a sensible period for stability checks. Another possibility is to perform a stability check before each measurement, if the chamber is used infrequently. In case when a chamber is shipped to another laboratory (e.g. for calibration), it is recommended to perform stability checks before and after shipping the chamber. Stability checks should also be performed in case of unexpected indications of the reference chamber or monitor chamber (based on the previous measurements), because they can indicate problems with the X-ray system or a chamber.

Stability checks are performed using a dedicated check source or other reproducible measurement setups. Reproducibility of the setup is considered good if its influence is much smaller than the expected instability of the chamber response. Modern X-ray generators usually show excellent stability over time, so irradiation at a fixed distance, with fixed geometry and radiation quality can in some cases be used for stability checks. If a gamma irradiator is available, it can also be used if the reproducibility requirements are fulfilled. If a radioactive source is used, corrections for half-life should be applied.

Stability check results are used to evaluate chamber stability. It is common to calculate standard deviation (standard uncertainty of the mean is not appropriate in this case) of all stability checks, or alternately all stability checks after the last calibration or the repair.

3.4.6 Linearity of the reference chamber (or measurement system)

Ionization chambers have excellent linearity, unless the dose rates are very high and the influence of ion recombination becomes significant. The critical dose rate is usually stated in the technical documentation provided by the manufacturer.

Reference class electrometers can have significant non-linearity. It is usually stated in the technical documentation and typical values are $\pm 0.25\%$ or $\pm 0.5\%$, over the whole measurement range. Rectangular probability distribution can be assumed for this contribution.

It is also possible to calibrate the electrometer for different values of collected charge (or current), and to estimate the uncertainty due to non-linearity based on the calibration certificate.

3.4.7 Energy dependence of the reference chamber (or measurement system) and differences in radiation quality between the primary and secondary laboratory

Energy dependence of the reference class dosimeters is usually small. IAEA TRS 457 (IAEA, 2007) gives requirements for energy dependence to be better than $\pm 2.6\%$ over the whole range of radiation qualities.

Even though the SSDL and the PSDL to which it is traceable have nominally the same radiation qualities, there are still some spectral differences due to the small differences in tube voltage, filtration, tube aging, anode angle

etc. If the standard radiation qualities are properly validated, the HVLs are expected to be within 4.4 % of the nominal value (Hourdakis et al., 2015; IAEA, 2011). For a 4.4 % change in HVL, the corresponding change in calibration coefficient is usually very small, much smaller than 1 %, and in many cases can be ignored. The uncertainty due to the energy dependence can be estimated by investigating how the calibration coefficient changes in the proximity of the standard radiation quality used. This can be done, for example, by interpolating calibration coefficients.

If there is no direct traceability for the radiation quality that is used, then the calibration coefficient is calculated by interpolation. In that case, the uncertainty resulting from the interpolation should be estimated.

Monitor chambers usually have much worse energy dependence. In some cases, the calibration coefficients can change by 10 % or more for subsequent radiation qualities. However, monitor chambers are calibrated and used in the same laboratory, so the difference in radiation quality between the moment of calibration and use is expected to be very small.

3.4.8 Correction for air density

Correction for air density depends on temperature and pressure measurements, but also on the difference in temperature between the thermometer and the sensitive volume of the chamber. This uncertainty contribution is also a combined uncertainty. Measurement procedures and equipment should be analysed to identify all significant contributions, which may include: calibration factors of the thermometer and barometer, repeatability and resolution of the measurements, change of temperature during the measurement etc. If the same thermometer and barometer are used to correct the indications of the reference chamber and monitor chamber, and the dose measurements are performed simultaneously, then all the uncertainties cancel out (they are completely correlated), with the exception of the uncertainty due to the difference in temperature between the thermometer and the chambers. The uncertainties do not cancel during XMM measurements, because the correction for air density is not performed for XMMs. However, the environmental conditions (especially temperature) can still influence the XMM and related uncertainty should be also considered.

3.4.9 Distance from the focus

Dose and dose rate decrease with the square of the distance from the focus (this is only an approximation, because the absorption in air and scattered radiation slightly affect this dependence). In principle, the reference chamber and the user dosimeter are positioned at the same distance from the focus. However, due to the imperfect positioning or imperfect knowledge of the reference point of the detector, there are always some small differences in positioning. The uncertainty of the positioning should be evaluated based on the positioning system (lasers, telescopes) employed and the experience of the metrologist. This uncertainty component has the sensitivity coefficient of 2.

3.4.10 Field non-uniformity

The influence of field non-uniformity is complex and is usually not treated rigorously. A necessary prerequisite to evaluate the influence of field non-uniformity is to measure the beam profile (e.g. using a small volume chamber that is moved across the beam, along two axes). Beam profile, in principle, depends on the collimator, distance from the focus and radiation quality, but in practice, it is usually determined only for a small number of conditions. Beam profile should be measured in the conditions in which the dosimeters are usually calibrated (e.g. at 1 m, 10 cm x 10 cm field size, RQR5, and at least the lowest and highest radiation quality).

If the reference chamber and the dosimeter under calibration are of the same size and shape, the influence of field non-uniformity can be neglected. In the other extreme, the influence is the largest if the differences between the devices are large. In addition, in case of XMMs the size of the whole dosimeter does not matter, but

the size and layout of detector elements and the resulting viewing angle will define how the XMM sees the field non-uniformity.

The uncertainty can be limited by using only the part of the beam with the required uniformity, e.g. within the 99 % isodose line. In this example, it can be estimated that the influence of non-uniformity is always lower than ± 0.5 % (extreme case of a point dosimeter, and a dosimeter that has the dimensions of the 99 % isodose line). Rectangular distribution can be assumed in this case. Uncertainty is almost always overestimated using this approach.

3.4.11 Stability of the measurement setup

The calibration is reliant on the reproducibility of the setup: radiation quality, distance from the focus, the field size, the scattering conditions. The time between the calibration of the monitor chamber and the calibration of the user instrument can be days or months, so all these parameters can change, if care is not taken. Radiation quality can change due to the tube aging (this can be mitigated by performing regular calibrations), change of filtration (if the filters are moved or damaged) and change in tube voltage. Field size can change if the collimators are replaced for different calibrations, or if the tube housing is opened in the meantime (e.g. for maintenance). In some laboratories, the X-ray tube housing may be moved along the rails, perpendicular to the beam axis, to allow using one calibration bench with multiple irradiators.

The measurement setup uncertainty can be estimated by performing a series of measurements, while repeating the complete setup between each two measurements. For example, filter wheels are removed, collimators are replaced, chamber is repositioned, voltage and current are reset etc. (the laboratory should assess which parts of the assembly are likely to be moved in the relevant timeframe). Standard deviation of these measurements gives a measure of the reproducibility of the setup. It is likely that the uncertainty is underestimated when using this method, because some effects can't be checked (e.g. tube aging or long term stability of the high voltage).

3.4.12 Other sources of uncertainty

Other sources of uncertainty are usually negligible for SSDL level calibration, but they should be checked, and the conclusions should be documented. Examples of other sources of uncertainty are differences in the field size and calibration distance between the SSDL and PSDL, air humidity, saturation correction etc.

3.5 Example uncertainty budget

3.5.1 Calibration by substitution using a secondary standard

In this example, a secondary standard is used to directly calibrate another ionization chamber. Calibration factor of the chamber is taken from the calibration certificate. Electrometer linearity is taken from the user manual. Chamber stability is known due to regular stability checks. Field uniformity is better than 99 % in the area that is used for measurements by reference and user chamber. Temperature difference between the chamber and the electrometer is estimated at 0.2 K, and temperature change during the calibration is 0.2 K. Barometer resolution is 0.5 mbar and the indication doesn't change during the measurements. Uncertainty of the positioning is estimated at 1 mm. Uncertainty of the calibration factor of the thermometer, the barometer and the meter tape is negligible (lower than 0.1 %), and is also correlated, because the same instruments are used during both reference and user measurements. The uncertainty budget for this scenario is presented in Table 3.1. The combined expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for this example is 1.7 %.

3.5.2 Calibration using a calibrated monitor chamber

In the second example, a calibrated monitor chamber is used to calibrate an XMM. The uncertainty of the monitor chamber calibration coefficient is equal to the combined uncertainty calculated in the first example. The stability is a little bit worse than for the reference chamber, because it is checked by performing repeated calibrations of the monitor chamber. There is an influence of the stability of measurement setup, because even though the same nominal setup must be used, the collimators, the filter wheels and other components of the setup may be replaced several times between the monitor chamber calibration and XMM calibration (e.g. to perform maintenance or to perform other types of calibrations). The user instrument has worse repeatability, and resolution becomes a significant contribution to the uncertainty budget, but the air density correction is not performed for the user instrument. Other contributions remain the same. The uncertainty for the second scenario is presented in Table 3.2. The combined expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for this example is 2.2 %.

Table 3.1. Example uncertainty budget for calibration by substitution using a secondary standard

No	Quantity, source of uncertainty	Value	Expanded absolute uncertainty, U_i	Unit	Probability distribution	Coverage factor	Standard relative uncertainty, u_i	Sensitivity, c_i
1 Reference measurement assembly								
1-1	Calibration factor	7.973	0.104	mGy/nC	Normal	2	0.65 %	1
1-2	Stability	38.25	0.24	mGy/min	Normal	2	0.32 %	1
1-3	Non-linearity	1	0.0025	/	Rectangular	1.73	0.14 %	1
2 Measurement setup and radiation quality								
2-1	Spectral difference PSDL - SSDL	1	0.003	/	Rectangular	1.73	0.17 %	1
2-2	Field uniformity	1	0.005		Rectangular	1.73	0.29 %	1
3 Determination of reference value								
3-1	Repeatability	5.11	0.01	nC/min	Normal	2	0.10 %	1
3-2	Temperature	292.16	0.28	K	Rectangular	1.73	0.06 %	1
3-3	Air pressure	1010.5	0.5	mbar	Rectangular	1.73	0.03 %	1
4 User chamber measurements								
4-1	Repeatability	9.95	0.02	nC/min	Normal	2	0.10 %	1
4-2	Temperature	292.26	0.28	K	Rectangular	1.73	0.06 %	1
4-3	Air pressure	1010.5	0.5	mbar	Rectangular	1.73	0.03 %	1
5 User chamber positioning								
5-1	Source to chamber distance	1000	1	mm	Rectangular	1.73	0.06 %	2
Combined uncertainty							0.84 %	

Table 3.2. Example uncertainty budget for calibration using a calibrated monitor chamber

No	Quantity, source of uncertainty	Value	Expanded absolute uncertainty, U_i	Unit	Probability distribution	Coverage factor	Standard relative uncertainty, u_i	Sensitivity, c_i
1 Reference measurement assembly								
1-1	Calibration factor	240.6	4.1	$\mu\text{Gy/nC}$	Normal	2	0.84 %	1
1-2	Stability	240.6	1.9	$\mu\text{Gy/nC}$	Normal	2	0.40 %	1
1-3	Non-linearity	1	0.0025	/	Rectangular	1.73	0.14 %	1
2 Measurement setup and radiation quality								
2-1	Change in the measurement setup	1	0.0078	/	Normal	2	0.39 %	1
2-2	Field uniformity	1	0.005		Rectangular	1.73	0.29 %	1
3 Determination of reference value								
3-1	Repeatability	13.07	0.02	nC	Normal	2	0.08 %	1
3-2	Temperature	292.16	0.28	K	Rectangular	1.73	0.06 %	1
3-3	Air pressure	1010.5	0.5	mbar	Rectangular	1.73	0.03 %	1
4 User instrument measurements								
4-1	Repeatability	3.16	0.01	mGy	Normal	2	0.16 %	1
4-2	Resolution	3.16	0.005	mGy	Rectangular	1.73	0.09 %	1
5 User instrument positioning								
5-1	Source to chamber distance	1000	1	mm	Rectangular	1.73	0.06 %	2
Combined uncertainty							1.09 %	

4 Calibration of XMMs in terms of PPV

4.1 Scope and general considerations

One of the activities of the TraMeXI project investigated the needs for the uncertainty of calibration coefficients for different quantities. This activity concluded that the uncertainty for tube voltage calibration derived from clinical needs is 1 % ($k = 2$). This uncertainty must be valid for clinical conditions. In the scope of the project, it was not considered how to derive the quantities of interest (PPV, kVp) from waveform measurements, so this guidance is limited to constant potential generators and to kVp. For constant potential generators, kVp and PPV approach the same numerical values.

Further input to this guidance was obtained by collecting calibration procedures from manufacturers as part of the TraMeXI project activities:

- The information available is limited to three manufacturers (PTW, RaySafe, RTI)
- Manufacturers (PTW, RaySafe, RTI) use calibrated high voltage dividers
 - The voltage dividers are usually calibrated at NMIs, e.g. PTB and NIST, or at an accredited calibration laboratory (RTI).

Additional information was collected from IBA during the M9 project meeting:

- IBA uses an XMM calibrated at PTB and a voltage divider. The voltage divider was calibrated by RadCal. The voltage divider is used for calibrations, the results are checked with XMM for QA.

Finally, several project partners provided details about their measurement procedures as inputs for this guidance. Table 4.1 gives information about the collected measurement procedures.

Table 4.1. Calibration procedures for tube voltage quantities

Institute	Reference	Distance [cm] ^a	Radiator	kV range ^a	Procedure	Uncertainty KCDB	Traceability KCDB
CMI		~95	ISOVOLT 160 HS with a MB 161/4 X-ray tube	7.5 - 300	CdTe detector calibrated with spectral lines from known radionuclides.	-	-
PTB	High voltage divider	~55	Industrial x-ray generators and tubes with ripple below 1 %	7.5 - 400	Calibration against voltage divider.	-	PTB
PTW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DYNALYZER high voltage unit (Machlett) • Sigma 30 Oszilloskop (Nicolet) • HDO4022 (Teledyn LeCroy) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epsilon 150 • Epsilon 2 • Mammomat 	23 - 150	Calibration against DYNALYZER.	-	-
RaySafe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluke 289 Voltmeter • Parker Medical H0917 voltage divider 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 (radioscopy) • 60 (mammography) • 195 (fluoroscopy) 		18 - 150	Calibration against internal voltage divider (working standard) that is calibrated against external voltage divider.	-	-
RTI	Radcal HV-1 high voltage divider system	50 - 110	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sedecal SHF 1030-M with Varian M-113R Mo tube (mammography), • Sedecal SHF 535 with Varian RAD14 with W tube. 		Calibration against internal voltage divider (working standard) that is calibrated against external voltage divider.	-	-
VSL		150	320 kV Comet Yxlon Y.TU 320-D03/MXR-320/26AX with ripple < 0.5 %	50 - 300	HPGe detector calibrated with spectral lines from known radionuclides	1.2 %	VSL
STUK Clinical	Clinical system: Dynalyzer	100	Indico	40 -120	Calibration against DYNALYZER.	-	-
STUK Industrial	Industrial system: FGH, Eng. & Test Gmbh Ge HV divider+DCV-meter and spectrometry (HP-Ge)	100	ISOVOLT 160 HS and 320 HS	10 - 200	Calibrated voltage divider (spectrometer is used for QA)	-	-
VINS	PTW Diavolt Universal T43014	100	Hopewell Designs X80-225 kV-E with Comet MXR-225/22 tube	25-150	Calibration against non-invasive high-voltage measuring device	-	PTB
ENEA-INMRI	GE Waygate Technologies high-voltage divider	50 - 100	GE Waygate Technologies Industrial x-ray generators and tubes with ripple below 1 %	5 - 450	Calibration against voltage divider	-	-

^a for calibration

4.2 Procedure

4.2.1 Reference Conditions

In this section, reference conditions are the conditions under which calibration results (including uncertainty) are reported. In contrast, measurement conditions are the conditions under which calibration is performed. Measurement conditions may differ from reference conditions. Deviations shall be expressed in terms of correction factors or included in the uncertainty budget. The reference conditions for the calibration procedure are presented in table 4.2

Table 4.2. Reference conditions

Voltage waveform	Constant potential
Anode angle	none ^a (diagnostic), 20° (mammography)
Filtration	RQR (diagnostic), 50 μm Rh (mammography), RQT (CT), 1.5 mm Al (dental)
Field size	3/2 * detector size (50 % isodose)
Detector-focal distance	40 cm
Temperature	20 °C
Scatter conditions	Free in air
Anode material	Tungsten

^a There is no need for a reference anode angle when using RQR. This is because RQR is defined based on a procedure that includes setting the additional filtration to mimic a reference x-ray tube.

4.2.2 Reference value

The reference value shall be derived from the displayed value of the internal voltage divider of the generator. The internal voltage divider must be adjusted based on:

- an invasive measurement using a traceable voltage divider connected to a digital voltmeter,
- or a measurement of the maximum photon energy (E_{\max}) with a CdTe or HP-GE spectrometer and a traceable determination of kVp by the equation: $kVp = \frac{E_{\max}}{e}$, where e is the elementary charge, this procedure is described in detail in literature (Šolc et al., 2025),
- or a traceable XMM, calibrated for the described diagnostic reference conditions, that is used to calibrate the internal voltage divider utilizing the same radiation conditions as during the calibration of the XMM.

4.2.3 Uncertainty budgets

The given uncertainty budgets shall include an uncertainty that accounts for the differences between the measurement conditions for a calibration and the reference conditions. Differences in radiation conditions are expressed as a correction factor k_Q .

4.2.3.1 Working standard voltage divider calibrated against external voltage divider

The uncertainty budget for the working standard voltage divider calibrated against an external voltage divider is given in table 4.3.

Table 4.3. The uncertainty budget for the working standard voltage divider calibrated against an external voltage divider

	Component	Example RTI [%]^{a, b}	Example PTB^a
External reference (voltage divider)	Calibration external Reference	0.025	0.022 %
	Nonlinearity compensation	0.01	
	Stability A/D converter	0.03	
	Long time stability external reference	0.01	14 V
Working standard (voltage divider)	Calibration procedure working standard	0.05	^d
	Resolution internal reference		29 V
	Long time stability internal reference	0.032	^d
XMM	Calibration procedure XMM	0.101	0.041 %
	Radiation Quality	0.25	^c
Combined uncertainty		0.28	0.062 %^c

^a $k = 1$

^b uncertainties are related to clinical machines, not the reference conditions described in this document

^c calculated for 70 kV

^d external voltage divider is connected to generator during the calibration

^e measurement conditions are equal to reference conditions

4.2.3.2 Working standard voltage divider calibrated against a CdTe spectrometer

The uncertainty budget for the working standard voltage divider calibrated against a CdTe spectrometer is given in table 4.4.

Table 4.4. The uncertainty budget for the working standard voltage divider calibrated against a CdTe spectrometer

	Component	Example CMI^a
CdTe spectrometry	Energy calibration curve	0.06 keV
	Energy calibration stability in time	0.05 keV
	Energy calibration at different count rate	0.1 keV
	Energy resolution and charge carrier transport influence	0.01 %
	Fit of high-energy part of measured spectrum	0.1 %
Combined uncertainty		0.21 %^b

^a $k = 1$

^b calculated for 70 kV

4.2.3.3 Working standard voltage divider calibrated against XMM

This example considers an XMM calibrated by another laboratory for the diagnostic reference conditions (Table 4.5). The instrument is used to calibrate the internal voltage divider of the generator under diagnostic reference

radiation conditions. Later, the calibration of the customer device will be performed by dividing the value shown by the generator's internal voltage divider by the displayed value of the customer device. Differences based on the x-ray tube angle and age are considered small because they are compensated by using IEC RQR reference conditions. Temperature and humidity are maintained close to the reference conditions. The influence of small changes in temperature and humidity, but also in the angle of incidence is included in the uncertainty due to the long-term stability.

Table 4.5. The uncertainty budget for the working standard voltage divider calibrated against an XMM

	Component	Example VINS [%] ^{a, b}
Calibration factor		0.062 %
Repeatability		<0.1 %
Resolution		<0.1 %
Long-term stability	Based on the repeated measurements in the same conditions at VINS	0.60 %
Combined uncertainty		0.62 %

^a $k = 1$

^b under the assumption, that traceability is given by an XMM transfer instrument calibrated for diagnostic reference conditions as reported by PTB in 4.2.3.1.

4.3 Comparison with target uncertainty

The exemplary uncertainty budgets for calibration factors determined at the reference conditions range from 0.062 % to 0.62 % ($k = 1$), depending on how traceability is established. If the XMM has been tested according to IEC 61676:2023, an additional uncertainty of up to 2.5 % ($k = 1$) can be expected for clinical measurements. This value alone exceeds the target uncertainty (1.0 % at $k = 2$). Suggestions on how to achieve the target uncertainty are described in 4.4.2.

4.4 Notes

4.4.1 Suggestions for lower uncertainties in clinical practice

To achieve the target uncertainty under clinical conditions, the calibrations of XMM that will be used under clinical conditions must be performed for measurement conditions that are close to the clinical conditions. A good example is the traceability chain given as an example by RTI, where the calibration is performed at a clinical machine.

Therefore, possibilities for a PSDL and SSDL to give traceability for kV measurements with an XMM, holding the target uncertainty, is

1. to perform the calibration of the XMM under radiation conditions that are very close to the clinical conditions of the customer (considering the x-ray tube of the user, the field size and the distance),
2. or to establish radiation conditions at the clinical machine under consideration that are close to the reference conditions described in this document.

4.4.2 Approaching clinical conditions with industrial x-ray tubes.

An approach to mimic clinical conditions with an industrial tube is to choose the same target-filter combination as the clinical device under consideration and mimic the difference in inherent filtration and anode angle by additional aluminium filtration.

In the following example (Figure 4.1) a spectrum was first simulated with Spekpy using anode angles of 12° and 20° . Then the 20° spectrum was attenuated with additional aluminium filtration, and the thickness providing the best match with the 12° spectrum was found.

Figure 4.1. Example provided by J. Tikkanen (STUK) – simulation of anode angle by adding aluminium filtration

An alternative approach to mimic low anode angles could be based on performing measurements off-axis. The following example (Figure 4.2) shows a spectrometric measurement on beam axis and about 5° off-axis on the left, right, above, and below.

Figure 4.2. Example provided by J. Šolc (CMI) – spectrometry measurements off-axis

5 Calibration of XMMs in terms of HVL

The summary presented in this section provides an overview of data collected and research carried out within the TraMeXI project. First, a survey was conducted among participating laboratories to assess the current practices for HVL measurement and calibration; the main findings of this survey are summarized here. Second, an extensive programme of experimental measurements and methodological analysis was performed, leading to the preparation and submission of a scientific manuscript on the calibration of X-ray multimeters for half-value layer determination (Tietäväinen et al., 2026). This section summarizes the key outcomes of both the survey and the manuscript. The objective is to propose a harmonized approach to HVL measurement and calibration and to provide input for the update of IAEA TRS-457. Detailed methodologies, experimental results, and uncertainty analyses are presented in the referenced publication.

5.1 Existing HVL measurement and calibration methods at laboratories

Questionnaire on HVL measurement and calibration in PSDLs and SSDLs

A questionnaire was conducted to assess the current practices in measuring and calibrating the HVL in various laboratories. Responses were received from nine laboratories –three PSDLs and six SSDLs, categorized based on their air kerma standards. Below is a summary of the findings:

Chambers and qualities used for measuring HVL

- For measuring HVL with mammographic qualities, the following ionization chambers were used: two PTW 34069 (W/Mo, W/Al, W/Ag), Radcal RC6M (W/Al, Mo/Mo), free-air chamber PK100N, and Exradin Magna A600. Four laboratories did not specify the ionization chambers used.
- For diagnostic qualities, the chambers used were: four Exradin A3 (RQR, RQT), two PTW 34069, and three free-air chambers (MEFAC (RQR, RQA, RQT), PK100N, GSS).

Miscellaneous findings

- Eight laboratories use a 1 m measuring distance for air kerma, while others reported distances of 1.5 m, 2 m, or between 0.3 and 2 m.
- Frequency of HVL measurement varies: one laboratory measures HVL "only once," three report a frequency of 1-5 years, and one measures "once in a while," especially after abnormal constancy test results. Some HVLs may not be measured at all.
- Only one laboratory provided an uncertainty budget for mammography HVL.
- None of the laboratories currently offer HVL calibration services, although client demand exists.

HVL measurement set-up

- Seven laboratories use a 1 m distance for HVL measurement, while others reported distances of 1.5 m or a range between 0.3 m and 1.5 m.
- Field width at the HVL measurement distance for ionizing chambers ranged from 5.5 cm to 12.5 cm, while for free-air chambers, it varied between 2 cm and 15 cm. One free-air chamber had a small opening of 0.5 cm. The relevance of free-air chamber openings as field size was questioned.

- The order of the HVL measurement setup, including filters, collimators, and monitor chambers, was discussed (details available in the questionnaire).

Monitor chamber usage

- Six laboratories do not use a monitor chamber to correct for tube output, while two do, and one bases its use on tube stability.
- Seven laboratories track monitor values to ensure stable tube output.
- Two laboratories observe clear changes in monitor values when HVL filtration is added, one reports no change, and one is unsure.

Air Kerma (K_a) measurements for HVL calculations

- Five laboratories perform 4-6 air kerma measurement points per HVL, one measures three points, and one takes a minimum of six points. Two laboratories repeat air kerma measurements without HVL filters.
- Four laboratories interpolate HVL using 3-5 air kerma points, while others use six or fewer, or a range of 2-4 or more than five points.
- Laboratories vary in how close the air kerma values are to the HVL target. One aims for <1 % deviation (accepting < 2 %), while others range between 0.5 % - 20 % or aim for specific precision (e.g., within 0.01 mm Al, 0.1 mm Al, or 1 mm Al).
- Eight laboratories require that air kerma points be measured on both sides of the HVL value.
- Equations for fitting HVL measurements differ: three laboratories use a fit based on the Beer-Lambert law ($K_a = K_{a,0}e^{-\mu x}$), while three apply a linear fit.
- Six laboratories include $K_{a,0}$ (air kerma without HVL filters) in the fit, while three do not.

Energy dependence of the ionization chamber

- Two laboratories consider energy dependence, one plans to address it in the future, and five do not take it into account.
- Three laboratories use (or plan to use) simulations to address energy dependence; one considers free-air chambers sufficiently independent.

Zero-field correction

- None of the laboratories perform zero-field correction. There was a question regarding whether this correction is necessary for free-air chambers.

HVL filters and traceability

- The thickness of individual aluminum filters used by the laboratories ranges from 0.005 mm to 11.21 mm. Specific ranges reported include: 0.01-1 mm, 0.05-1 mm, 0.2-10 mm, 0.01-11.21 mm, and 0.005-10 mm.
- Five laboratories rely on the nominal filter thickness provided by the manufacturer, while four do not.

- One laboratory estimates filter thickness using a known radius and precision balance, while four laboratories measure filter thickness at 5-10 positions with a micrometer or caliper.
- Filter manufacturers mentioned include Goodfellow (3 responses), ESPI Metals (2), PTB, PTW, Alfa Aesar, VUK-Ciste kovy, and Drijfhout Edelmetaalbedrijven BV. Tolerances were noted for Goodfellow and VUK-Ciste kovy filters.
- Five laboratories do not consider filter uniformity, while four do. Those that considered uniformity measured it with a micrometer or caliper.
- All laboratories used the nominal purity of filters as stated by the manufacturer.

5.1.1 Summary of existing HVL measurement/calibration methods at laboratories

Current HVL practices at Primary and Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratories (PSDLs and SSDLs) show substantial variation in measurement geometry, instrumentation, and data evaluation procedures. Most laboratories determine HVL using reference-class ionization chambers and aluminum filters, with air kerma measurements performed at distances typically around 1 m. Both free-in-air and collimated narrow-beam geometries are used, often without explicit correction for field-size effects or chamber energy dependence.

Questionnaire results collected within the TraMeXI project indicate that laboratories differ in:

- the number of air-kerma measurement points used for HVL determination,
- the fitting method applied (linear interpolation versus exponential attenuation),
- the consideration of ionization-chamber energy dependence.

Most laboratories rely on nominal filter thicknesses provided by manufacturers, and only one reports a full uncertainty budget for HVL (for mammography). At present, dedicated HVL calibration services for X-ray multimeters (XMMs) are rarely offered, despite increasing clinical use and user demand.

These findings highlight the need for harmonized procedures, particularly regarding beam geometry, traceability, and uncertainty evaluation, which are addressed in the present deliverable and described in detail in the associated journal article.

5.2 Existing HVL measurement and calibration methods *in guides*

International guidance on HVL measurement is provided primarily in:

- IAEA TRS-457 (IAEA, 2007)
- Implementation of IAEA TRS-457 (Review of the test results) (IAEA, 2011)
- IEC 61267 (Annex B) (IEC, 2025)
- ICRU Report 10b (ICRU, 1962)
- ICRU Report 74 (ICRU, 2005)
- ISO 4037-1 (radiation protection, refers to ICRU 10b) (ISO, 2019)

These documents define HVL and outline basic measurement principles, emphasizing narrow-beam geometry and the use of aluminum filters. However, they provide limited guidance on data evaluation methods, energy dependence of detectors, field-size effects, and comprehensive uncertainty estimation. Zero-field correction is addressed in ISO 4037-1, where it is recommended for beams above 100 kV. In diagnostic radiology no

corresponding energy-based recommendation is given; ICRU Report 74 notes the approach of Trout et al., i.e. linear extrapolation of HVL to zero field size.

The work summarized here builds on this framework, remaining consistent with existing recommendations while proposing clarifications and extensions relevant to modern calibration practice and XMM use. These proposals are intended as input for future updates of TRS-457.

5.3 Methodology to establish the HVL reference value

The reference half-value layer is established by measuring air kerma with a reference-class ionization chamber under narrow-beam conditions and determining the aluminum thickness that reduces the unattenuated air-kerma rate to 50 %. Measurements are performed using several filter thicknesses selected close to the first-HVL value, and the HVL is obtained by regression of a locally linearized attenuation curve.

Based on the results presented in Tietäväinen et al. (2026), the following methodological principles are recommended for establishing a reference HVL:

- Energy dependence of the ionization chamber should be considered.
 - The addition of HVL filters modifies the X-ray spectrum through beam hardening, which may change the applicable air-kerma calibration coefficient of the ionization chamber.
 - This effect can be significant, particularly for lower tube voltages.
 - The methodology therefore requires the use of a reference-class ionization chamber with well-characterized energy dependence and, where possible, calibration coefficients for both standard and non-standard (HVL-filtered) radiation qualities, or a justified method for estimating the associated correction and its uncertainty.
- HVL should be measured under narrow-beam conditions, with the beam as small as reasonably achievable while still fully covering the sensitive volume of the ionization chamber.
 - For higher-energy radiation qualities, the influence of scattered radiation becomes increasingly significant.
 - To evaluate this effect, HVL measurements at different field sizes (preferably at least 3) should be used to assess field-size dependence, and extrapolation to zero field should be applied when a clear trend is observed.
 - The resulting zero-field-corrected HVL is taken as the reference value, and the uncertainty associated with the extrapolation is included in the uncertainty budget.
- Air-kerma measurements should be taken at several filter thicknesses close to the HVL value.
 - The thicknesses should be within $\pm 5\%$ but at most $\pm 10\%$ of the 50 % attenuation level.
- A locally linearized attenuation model, based on a modified form of the Beer–Lambert law, should be applied to these measurement points.
 - The unattenuated air-kerma value should be measured to define the HVL but excluded from the regression fit.

5.4 HVL calibration methodology

In HVL calibration of X-ray multimeters, the reference HVL determined with an ionization chamber serves as the calibration input quantity. The manuscript demonstrates that, unlike ionization chambers, modern XMMs are largely insensitive to scattered radiation and field size, provided a sufficiently large irradiation field is used.

Based on these findings, the following calibration approach is recommended:

- The reference HVL is determined under narrow-beam conditions using an ionization chamber, applying corrections for energy dependence and, when necessary, zero-field effects.
- The XMM calibration in terms of HVL is performed under the same conditions as air-kerma calibration, typically in a broad beam and without an HVL collimator (e.g. 10 cm x 10 cm).
- The calibration coefficient transfers the XMM-measured HVL to the equivalent narrow-beam (reference) HVL value.

This approach reflects both laboratory metrology requirements and typical clinical measurement conditions, while maintaining compatibility between reference and user measurements.

5.5 Traceability estimation

Traceability of HVL measurements is achieved through two primary chains:

1. Air-kerma measurement, performed with a reference-class ionization chamber calibrated at a PSDL and traceable to the SI.
2. HVL filter thickness, determined either from manufacturer certificates meeting metrological requirements or from direct measurements (e.g. micrometer or mass-based methods) traceable to dimensional and mass standards.

Because HVL is derived from a ratio of air-kerma measurements, many systematic components cancel; however, residual effects—particularly ionization-chamber energy dependence—remain and must be included in the uncertainty evaluation. When these traceable inputs are combined consistently, the resulting HVL reference values are directly linked to primary standards.

5.6 Estimating the uncertainty budget

The manuscript presents a structured uncertainty approach in three steps:

1. Measured HVL uncertainty, incorporating uncertainties of air-kerma ratios and filter thickness, propagated through linear regression.
2. Reference HVL uncertainty, including reproducibility and uncertainty associated with zero-field correction.
3. HVL calibration coefficient uncertainty, combining reference HVL uncertainty with the XMM measurement uncertainty.

For diagnostic radiology qualities, the dominant contributors are:

- ionization-chamber energy dependence,
- filter thickness determination, and

- field-size dependence at higher effective energies.

Weighted total least-squares regression is recommended when uncertainties in both variables are significant. For routine calibration work, the manuscript also discusses the possibility of simplified, conservative uncertainty evaluations focusing on dominant terms.

5.7 Results and discussion of the reference HVL and its uncertainty

Using the methodology described above, reference HVLs were established for RQR 2, RQR 5, and RQR 10 radiation qualities. For RQR 2 and RQR 5, zero-field correction was found to be unnecessary, while for RQR 10 it produced a measurable improvement in consistency with independent spectrometric HVL values.

The expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) of the reference HVLs were approximately 1–2 %, increasing with beam hardness due to field-size effects. The corresponding uncertainties of HVL calibration coefficients for XMMs remained below 2 %, well within the 5 % accuracy target typically considered adequate for clinical use.

Comparison with spectrometry and model-based calculations showed agreement within stated uncertainties, supporting the validity of the proposed approach. Detailed numerical results, figures, and uncertainty distributions are provided in the associated journal article, which should be cited as the primary technical reference.

6 Other quantities measured by XMMs

Calibration and measurement procedures for other quantities measured by XMMs (other than air kerma, HVL and tube voltage) are not discussed in detail in this document. Calibration needs and overview of calibration services in Europe are available in the paper published by Komatina et al. (2025), which sums up several activities of the TraMeXI project.

7 Use of XMMs in clinical measurements

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents harmonised, practical procedures for the use of X-ray multimeters in clinical measurements and for performing clinical cross-calibrations where required. The objective is to ensure that measurement results are comparable across sites and over time, while maintaining a clear metrological link to traceable reference standards.

XMMs have become routine instruments for clinical measurements due to their compact design, rapid readout, and ability to indicate multiple quantities—such as air kerma, air-kerma rate, tube voltage, HVL, exposure time, and filtration—within a single exposure (Komatina et al., 2025). However, much of the existing guidance has been developed primarily for ionisation chambers (ICs) (IAEA, 2007). The widespread adoption of semiconductor-based XMMs, combined with their reliance on embedded algorithms, introduces new requirements regarding measurement conditions, documentation, calibration strategies, and uncertainty evaluation. The XMMs have been extensively studied, especially under the TraMeXI project (Krzanovic et al., 2026; Salomon et al., 2020; Kojic et al., 2024; Costa de Castro et al., 2024; Salomon et al., 2025; Krzanovic et al., 2021; Stasko et al., 2025; Krzanovic et al., 2026, Tietäväinen et al., 2026, Kojic et al., 2026, Toroi et al., 2026). This section therefore updates and harmonises procedures to ensure that XMM-based results are consistent, traceable, and defensible in clinical practice.

Ionisation chambers remain the reference-class instruments for air-kerma-related quantities. Their energy dependence is small and well characterised, enabling reliable interpolation between calibrated radiation qualities. In contrast, semiconductor-based XMMs exhibit stronger intrinsic energy dependence. Manufacturers address this through multi-detector designs and software models that translate detector signals into indicated quantities. As a result, the indicated values depend not only on the radiation field but also on internal algorithms and user-selected parameters such as anode material, inherent and added filtration, tube-voltage range, and, in mammography, the presence of a compression plate. Consequently, XMMs should be calibrated under conditions that closely match their intended clinical use. Where calibration under appropriate conditions at a dedicated calibration laboratory is not available, an on-site cross-calibration may be performed, or the associated measurement uncertainty must be increased accordingly.

Compared to ionisation chambers, XMMs are generally less sensitive to scattered radiation because they are typically shielded against back- and side-scattered radiation. Conversely, XMMs are more sensitive to orientation, requiring accurate alignment of the entrance surface perpendicular to the central beam axis, and they may respond differently to scattered radiation depending on the effective viewing angle. For this reason, consistent geometry, field size and source-to-detector distance, together with thorough documentation of software settings, are essential to achieve reproducible and comparable measurements.

7.2 Harmonized measurement conditions

Reproducibility begins with repeatable measurement geometry and correct use of the XMM. The same geometry and software configuration shall be maintained throughout a measurement series and thoroughly documented to ensure that results remain comparable over time and across different X-ray systems. XMMs can measure multiple quantities and parameters within a single exposure, and in most cases the measurement setup does not need to be changed when switching between quantities. However, in specific cases, such as tube-voltage measurements, additional filtration or alternative software selections may be required. Users shall therefore always verify the manufacturer-specific requirements applicable to their XMM and the quantity being measured.

7.2.1 Measurement geometry

Measured values may be influenced by field size, XMM positioning within the X-ray field, and distance variations. The measurement geometry shall therefore be standardised and reproducible within tight tolerances. The X-ray field size should be fixed to ensure comparability and chosen as a compromise between minimising scatter and avoiding partial field shading. A field size of approximately 10 cm × 10 cm has been shown to be suitable for many applications.

The focus-to-sensor distance shall be kept constant across repeated measurements and across different devices. X-ray fields may exhibit intensity inhomogeneities of up to 25 %, making reproducible sensor positioning essential for meaningful comparisons over time.

The appropriate measurement geometry depends on the imaging modality and clinical application. Modality-specific recommendations are provided in the following chapter. For more detailed guidance, reference is made to the results of the corresponding TraMeXI activities on harmonised measurement and clinical calibration procedures, which are provided separately.

7.2.2 XMM positioning

Centre the sensor reference point in the beam using the laser or any other available positioning indicators and ensure that the entrance surface of the sensor is perpendicular to the beam axis. For XMMs, follow the manufacturer's instruction regarding orientation relative to the anode-cathode axis to minimize heel-effect bias. Note that the light field and the X-ray field may not be exactly aligned and can be offset from each other by up to 1 cm. Nevertheless, the most important requirement is reproducible positioning of the XMM so that the measured value represents the central-beam air kerma. If the XMM is positioned near the edge of the X-ray beam, the air-kerma value may differ substantially from that at the centre, and reproducible positioning may be difficult. Avoid positioning the XMM close to the callipers, as non-reproducible partial shadowing can degrade measurement quality. Also note that some XMMs have more than one possible sensor position; ensure that the correct sensor reference point is used consistently.

7.2.3 Scattering and attenuation conditions

XMMs are typically shielded against radiation incident from the back and sides and are therefore largely insensitive to backscattered radiation. When this is the case, they may be positioned directly on top of a phantom or supporting table. However, XMMs may still be affected by forward-scattered radiation, particularly when scattering objects such as filters are present in the beam. To minimise unwanted scatter contributions, all objects within approximately 30 cm of the primary beam that are not a fixed part of the system should be removed.

Components that are permanently integrated into the X-ray system (e.g. tube housing, compression paddle) should remain in place in order to replicate clinically relevant conditions. This also applies to under-couch tube installations, where the objective is to measure the air kerma of the X-ray beam after attenuation by the patient couch and incident on the patient. In such cases, the measurement must be performed under these specific conditions.

It should be noted that the patient couch acts as an additional filter, thereby modifying the X-ray spectrum. This affects parameters such as total filtration and HVL and may also influence voltage indications for certain XMMs. Care should be taken to achieve highly reproducible positioning of the patient couch, as couches are typically composed of non-uniform materials and may vary in thickness and composition in both the longitudinal and lateral directions. Furthermore, when an XMM is mounted on a stand, the distance between the exit plane of the patient couch and the entrance plane of the XMM must be kept constant, as variations in this distance can affect measurement results.

In specific cases where the measurement data are not intended for patient dosimetry but rather for quality assurance or assessment of system stability, alternative measurement conditions may be selected to minimise influencing factors. For example, to determine tube output without attenuation or scatter from the patient couch, a 90° tube tilt or an over-couch geometry may be preferable.

7.2.4 Standardized exposure conditions

The X-ray system should be operated in manual mode to ensure accurate and reproducible measurements. Automatic exposure control (AEC) shall not be used for quantitative verification, calibration, or cross-calibration procedures where precise and comparable results are required. The X-ray image detector

should be adequately protected (e.g. by copper sheets placed close to the detector entrance surface) in a manner that does not disturb the XMM measurements. Image acquisition and storage are not required for dosimetry measurements and should be disabled to prevent unnecessary system load or saturation.

When AEC performance itself is the subject of quality control, standardized phantoms and fixed, reproducible measurement conditions should be used. If an XMM is placed in the beam while AEC is active, it should be recognised that the dosimeter may influence the exposure outcome. The user should therefore determine the location and size of the AEC sensing area and position the XMM outside this region as far as possible, without compromising exposure of the primary beam. When comparing results across measurements or systems, the same XMM model should be used, and positioning should be reproducible. The most accurate air-kerma values are generally obtained by calculating air kerma from independently measured tube output rather than relying directly on AEC-driven readouts. Note that for some interventional X-ray systems, manual mode may only be available under service-level operating conditions.

Use sufficiently long exposure pulses (typically >100 ms), especially when time resolution is relevant or when pulsed exposures exhibit long rise and fall times. For extended measurement sessions, use of the large focal spot is often preferable; however, focal-spot size influences beam characteristics and measured quantities. Measurements should therefore be repeated using focal-spot sizes that are clinically relevant.

No air temperature or pressure correction is required for XMMs. Nevertheless, temperature can still affect detector response. Environmental conditions should therefore be kept as stable as possible, and accurate measurements should be avoided under extreme conditions (e.g. direct sunlight).

The waveform display should be checked for every measurement, particularly when results deviate from expectations. Several parameters reported by XMMs are derived from waveform analysis, and effects such as overlapping pulses in fluoroscopy systems or dose-rate fluctuations in mobile radiography units may lead to unexpected or unreliable results.

For paediatric protocols, ensure that the anti-scatter grid is removed.

7.2.5 XMM settings

Ensure that the exposure air kerma and air-kerma rate are within the rated operating ranges of the XMM for the quantity being measured. Aim for sufficiently high dose and dose-rate levels per exposure, as indications may become unstable when operating close to the lower limits of the specified measurement range. Be aware that different quantities measured by the XMM may have different manufacturer-specified ranges and, for some quantities, more stringent measurement conditions.

All relevant XMM software settings (e.g. anode/filter selection, modality, firmware and software version, special operating modes) shall be recorded, as these parameters directly affect the indicated quantities. Verify that the selected software configuration (including anode/filter combination and, for mammography, the presence or absence of a compression plate) corresponds to the actual beam conditions. Since the XMM response is dependent on the X-ray spectral shape, the same software settings shall be used for all repeated measurements and clearly documented to ensure meaningful comparison. If the correct selection is not available, the impact of using an incorrect setting should be evaluated and incorporated into the measurement uncertainty.

Select the reported quantities to be used for evaluation and apply this selection consistently across measurement sessions. XMM indications are sensitive to both measurement conditions and software configuration. Use pulse durations that the XMM can resolve reliably and routinely inspect waveform displays for artefacts such as overlapping pulses or transient edge effects. When appropriate, store waveform data to support later investigation of unexpected or inconsistent measurement results.

7.2.6 Measurement protocol

The XMM should be allowed to stabilise thermally and adapt to the environmental conditions before measurements are started. It is therefore recommended to bring the instrument into the examination room at

least 15 minutes prior to the beginning of the measurements. In addition, a pre-irradiation of the detector is advisable, and the first one or two exposures should not be used for quantitative evaluation. Some warm-up exposures of the X-ray tube may also be beneficial to ensure stable and reproducible operating conditions.

To assess the short-term repeatability of the measurement system, perform at least ten repeated measurements under one well-defined reference condition. The resulting relative standard deviation may be used for uncertainty estimation and to evaluate whether a higher number of repetitions is required for other measurement points. For routine measurements, a minimum of three repetitions per measurement point is recommended (two repetitions may be sufficient for very stable systems). However, if the variation between these repetitions is significantly larger than the typical repeatability determined under reference conditions, additional measurements shall be performed to maintain an acceptable level of measurement uncertainty.

The following step-by-step procedure is recommended for the measurements:

- Preparation
 - Allow the XMM to stabilize in the room for at least 15 minutes.
 - Set the X-ray system to manual exposure mode and disable AEC.
 - Protect the image receptor with suitable shielding and disable image storage.
 - Remove unnecessary scattering objects within approximately 30 cm of the beam.
 - Select the correct XMM settings (anode/filter, modality, software options).
- Geometry & Positioning
 - Set a reference focus-to-detector distance.
 - Adjust the field size to the selected reference field size at the XMM reference plane.
 - Place the XMM reference point at the center of the beam.
 - Orient the XMM entrance surface perpendicular to the beam axis and follow recommended orientation relative to the anode–cathode axis.
- Exposure Setup
 - Use pulse durations longer than 100 ms when possible.
 - Use the large focal spot unless small focal spot measurements are required to mimic clinical usage.
 - Ensure air kerma and kerma rate remain within the XMM’s rated ranges.
- Measurement Sequence
 - Perform a few preliminary exposures to stabilize detector response.
 - At one reference condition, record at least 10 repeated measurements to establish repeatability.
 - For each radiation quality, record at least 3 exposures; add more if variability is unusually high.
 - Keep exposure parameters and XMM settings identical across repeats.
 - Review the waveform display after each exposure to detect anomalies.
- Documentation
 - Basic data
 - Who performed the measurement?
 - What was measured?
 - Where was the measurement performed?
 - When was the measurement performed?
 - How was the measurement performed?
 - Equipment used
 - Reference instrument type and serial number
 - Calibrated XMM type / serial number

- Other items and equipment used (thermometer, barometer, phantom, attenuators)
- Measurement geometry
 - Distance from focus
 - Field size
 - X-ray system positioning
 - Attenuators: use of compression paddle or patient couch
 - Photos of the measurement setup have been proven helpful for measurements more elaborated than QC
 - Dosimeter positioning and orientation
- X-ray system settings
 - System data (model, type, serial number)
 - Anode, anode angle
 - Focus size
 - Inherent filtration
- Environmental conditions
 - Temperature, pressure
- Protocol
 - Tube current, exposure time, and/or their product
 - Radiation qualities: Tube voltage(s) and filtration(s) applied
- Measurement data
 - All recorded or relevant values, units
 - Software selections

7.3 Harmonized procedures for different modalities

7.3.1 Harmonized measurement procedures for radiography systems

In conventional radiology many distances and field sizes are used for clinical practice that have a clear impact on patient exposure. However, for accurate and comparable measurements a standardized distance from focus of 100 cm and field size 10 cm × 10 cm at the XMM reference plane are recommended.

7.3.2 Harmonized measurement procedures for fluoroscopy systems

Some radiography systems, such as C-arms, have a more limited range of possible measurement distances. Source to image detector distance should be maximized within practical limits to minimize the influence of scattered radiation at the measurement location. The selection of reference distance might be at the isocenter, the entrance cover of the image receptor housing or the patient entrance reference point which is 15 cm from the isocenter toward the X-ray tube. Be aware that the positioning influences the scatter component at the XMM. A reference field size 10 cm × 10 cm or equivalent at the reference distance is recommended.

Where applicable, the selected pulse width and pulse rate should be verified from the XMM waveform. Be aware that some C-arm devices exhibit deviations from set pulse rate at the end of a pulse train. When manual mode is not available, phantoms may be used to simulate patient absorption so that the AEC provides clinically relevant exposure settings. These attenuators should be positioned on the image detector side behind the dosimeter. PMMA or water-equivalent phantoms would provide better simulation of human body attenuation, but often there is a severe limitation in space, and it is better to use more strongly attenuating material like copper instead.

7.3.3 Harmonized measurement procedures for mammography systems

In mammography the distance and field sizes used in clinical practice are mostly fixed and therefore, the measurements are performed under these conditions. If the XMM is backscatter protected, it can be positioned directly on the breast support table. However, to avoid repeated exposure of the image receptor to primary beam and potential ghost images of the XMM, a copper plate or equivalent should be used for shielding. This will also standardize scattering conditions. The compression paddle should be raised to the highest possible position to harmonize the forward scattering conditions for different detectors.

Align the XMM entrance surface perpendicular to the central beam axis and orient it following the manufacturer's guidance. The XMM should be centred laterally to the beam. Following the new international recommendation, the reference distance from the chest wall edge is 50 mm along the midline (Sechopoulos et al., 2024). Confirm the focal spot-to-detector distance and keep it constant across repeats (usually fixed by the system).

In mammography, different anode-filter combinations are available and most XMMs require pre-selection of the applied radiation quality. In addition, there might be separate selections for the compression paddle being in or out. In mammography, it might not be possible to select tube current and time separately and a fixed tube loading (of e.g., 50 mAs) is recommended for tube output measurements.

8 Clinical calibrations of XMMs

Clinical calibrations link clinical measurement results to traceable standards. Because XMMs rely on device-specific algorithms and are more sensitive to spectral conditions, they should be calibrated under radiation qualities and geometries representative of clinical use. Where the laboratory calibration does not cover the clinical spectrum closely enough (e.g., different filter, anode angle), the user can perform an on-site cross-calibration against a traceable reference. If cross-calibration is not feasible, increase the uncertainty in line with the identified differences.

For calibration purposes, the most stable conditions should be applied. Therefore, it generally makes little sense to use challenging clinical conditions where e.g., manual selection of radiation quality is not possible or the positioning of XMM in a scatter free condition is not easy (C-arm), apart from conditions, e.g. hard filtered spectral settings, that cannot be realized elsewhere.

8.1 Reference values

In a calibration process, the link between the reference value and XMM response is studied under controlled and standardized conditions. The XMM measurement procedure is the same for all quantities, but the method used to obtain the reference value depends on the quantity. The reference value is measured with a device, which has a traceable calibration to national standards (SSDL, PSDL).

8.1.1 Air kerma

Establish a reference with a reference-class IC traceable to SSDL/PSDL. A reference-class IC should have small energy dependence, which allows interpolation between calibration radiation qualities. Typically, HVL is used as a radiation quality specifier for this interpolation. However, if a set of calibration coefficients for different tube voltages and filtrations is available, also these radiation quality specifiers can be used for the selection of a correct calibration coefficient. Uncertainty related to the interpolation should be included in the uncertainty budget and the energy dependence of response can be estimated based on the calibration data. Extrapolation outside of the calibrated range is not recommended.

For clinical cross-calibration of an XMM, use substitution at identical geometry (same field size, distance, beam center, orientation) and identical software settings as used clinically. Remember that the vented IC requires pressure–temperature correction. In addition, the difference in sensitivity for scatter of different dosimeters (IC vs. XMM) should be understood and considered. Optimally the calibration should be performed in beams with minimal scatter included.

8.1.2 Tube voltage

There are different tube voltage related quantities (see chapter 4). Therefore, it is important to understand, which quantity is used and if tube output variations impact the indicated values.

There are three methods to define the reference values:

- High voltage divider (invasive)
- Spectrometry
- Calibrated XMM

Spectral end-point energy can be determined with a suitable spectrometer, e.g. CdTe-detector (Šolc et al., 2025a; Šolc et al., 2025b; Šolc et al., 2026; Rinaldi et al., 2026). This method is very flexible and offers lots of additional information. There is, however, some relevant effort before reliable data can be achieved. Invasive measurement with a high voltage divider is probably the most accurate method if available and correctly calibrated. It is, however, normally not available at clinical installations. A calibrated XMM could also be

considered but in this case, the XMM should have a specific calibration for the specific condition, where the measurement is performed. Typically, calibrations are performed using IEC standard reference radiation qualities (RQR for radiography and fluoroscopy and RQR-M for mammography). It is important to perform the tube voltage calibrations in conditions like clinical conditions. For example, added copper filtration might significantly change the XMM indication.

8.1.3 HVL

The reference value for HVL can be calculated from measured spectra or measured using a reference-class IC (XMMs should not be used for this method) using sheets of Al of precisely known thickness and high purity. The HVL is defined in a narrow-beam and scatter free condition and therefore, the measurements should be performed in a field size as small as possible, considering that the IC sensitive area is still homogeneously irradiated.

In the IC method the HVL is determined using multiple aluminium sheets with thicknesses around the level where air kerma is halved. Use Al-sheets of individually determined thicknesses and sufficiently high purity, purity of more than 99.995 % is typical. Be aware that traces of heavy elements can substantially influence the HVL determination. The accuracy of aluminium sheet thickness and chamber energy dependence impact directly on the uncertainties. The Al-sheets should be positioned preferable in the middle between the IC and focus and an additional collimator should be used to limit the scatter from the Al-sheets. The air kerma measurements are performed so that the collimator is in place but without Al-shielding and then with at least three different sets of Al-sheets that provide air kerma values close to and on both sides of the half value. When no additional collimators are available, collimate the primary beam accordingly. Assure a field size of no more than 10 x 10 cm² at the plane of the IC.

Use air kerma values for HVL determination that are (ideally) at most 10 % deviating from half of the initial kerma value (without filters). If only larger deviations are possible, consider their influence in the uncertainty budget calculation. Use modified Lambert-Beer-formula with offset to fit HVL (i.e. the measurement point without added filtration is not used for interpolation, only the points close to HVL). The reference chamber reading has to be corrected for ionization chamber energy dependence, or otherwise this needs to be included in the uncertainty budget. If possible, use extra calibration points close to the radiation quality achieved by adding HVL filtration to the original radiation quality. More details about HVL calculations can be found in the calibration laboratory part of this deliverable.

8.2 Calibration process

Since the aim of clinical calibration is to get the calibration coefficients specifically for the clinical measurement condition, and it should be controlled and standardized, it is recommended to follow the measurement procedures introduced in the previous chapter. Pay extra effort to minimize stray objects close to the beam and be cautious to always use identical distance of the different dosimeters. Be aware that the reference plane is not always is the entrance plane of the dosimeter.

Here is a step-by-step procedure for calibrations:

- Preparation
 - Follow all preparation steps from the measurement procedure (warm up, manual mode, shielding, scatter control, correct XMM settings).
 - Ensure a traceable reference instrument (IC, spectrometer, or calibrated transfer XMM depending on quantity) is available and ready for use.
 - Verify that both the reference instrument and the XMM can operate within their rated air kerma and air kerma rate ranges at the selected measurement conditions.
- Establish the calibration geometry

- Set up the measurement geometry, preferably as described previously in the measurement procedure:
 - reference distance, 1 m focus to sensor distance is typical
 - reference field size, 10 cm x 10 cm has proven a good compromise
 - positioning and orientation,
 - scatter environment.
- If the reference instrument is an IC or another XMM, the XMM to be calibrated must be placed at the exact same reference point, one after the other, without changing geometry between them. Be aware that the reference plane of XMMs does not always correspond to the entrance plane.
- Mark the detector position or use positioning aids to ensure high reproducibility when swapping the devices.
- Determine the reference value (per quantity)
 - The reference value must be measured under the same irradiation conditions that are used for the XMM
 - Establish pulses of sufficient length, at least 100 ms.
 - Air kerma
 - Place the traceable ionization chamber at the defined reference point.
 - Zero the IC/electrometer, apply environmental corrections.
 - Perform several exposures and calculate the reference air kerma or kerma rate using the IC calibration coefficient (interpolated if needed).
 - Average repeated readings to obtain a stable reference value.
 - Tube voltage (kVp or PPV)
 - Select an appropriate reference method:
 - invasive high voltage divider, or
 - spectrometry (end point energy), or
 - a calibrated transfer XMM.
 - Perform exposures and calculate the reference tube voltage value (averaged).
 - Half value layer
 - Use one of the accepted reference methods:
 - ionization chamber HVL measurement (narrow beam method with aluminium filters), or
 - spectrometric HVL determination.
 - Determine the reference HVL.
- Measure the XMM
 - Remove the reference instrument without changing distance, field size, collimation, or orientation.

- Place the XMM at the exact same reference point and apply correct radiation quality and other selections in the XMM menu.
- Perform the minimum number of exposures defined in the measurement procedure (typically ≥ 3).
- Record the XMM indications for the calibrated quantity (air kerma, kVp/PPV, HVL).
- Calculate calibration coefficients
 - For each quantity Q , compute the calibration coefficient N_Q as:
$$N_Q = \frac{Q_{ref}}{Q_{XMM}}$$
 - Use average values from both the reference measurements (Q_{ref}) and XMM measurements (Q_{XMM}).
 - Document any corrections applied (e.g., reference quality interpolation or spectrum mismatch).
- Repeat for all required clinical beam qualities
 - Repeat steps for each clinically used anode/filter–kV combination, and for each focal spot if relevant.
 - Include at least one repeatability series per session (≥ 10 measurements) to evaluate short term stability.
- Documentation
 - Record
 - all reference values and how they were determined,
 - all XMM indications,
 - all calibration coefficients,
 - all geometry parameters,
 - all exposure settings,
 - all detector settings.
 - Note any deviations from the reference geometry and include them in the uncertainty evaluation.
- Prepare uncertainty budget

9 Use of data measured with XMMs

9.1 Quality control

XMM measurements are typically performed as a part of quality control procedures of X-ray systems. In this case the user should fix the measurement procedure and establish baseline references for the measured quantities. For XMMs, routinely review time resolved data to identify transient behaviour or pulse overlap that could bias numerical indications. Tube voltage and HVL are used to make sure that the spectral output remains stable over time. These measurements can also be used to check the accuracy of the value indicated by the X-ray system. For example, if the measured tube voltage starts to change when the nominal values remain the same, this can be an indication of a problem with the X-ray tube.

9.2 Patient dosimetry

Air kerma measurements can also be used as a starting point for patient dosimetry. Typically, air kerma measurements are used for tube output measurements where the air kerma / tube current-time product is measured for each radiation quality and relevant conditions. Then this data can be used to calculate air kerma for any tube current-time product and the values can be corrected for distance using the inverse square law. For skin dose or entrance surface air kerma calculations, appropriate back scatter factors should be applied. However, it should be kept in mind that these factors are also very dependent on the radiation quality and field size, so the actual condition required for patient exposure should be considered when this value is calculated. In mammography air kerma can be used together with HVL to calculate mean glandular dose (MGD).

9.3 Use of calibration certificates and other metrological data

Regular calibrations and/or verifications are essential to ensure that measurements performed with XMMs are accurate, traceable, and comparable. Calibration establishes the relationship between the dosimeter's indicated value and the corresponding conventional true value of the measured quantity as realised by a reference standard, including the associated measurement uncertainty. Calibration is distinct from adjustment or verification and always results in a stated uncertainty. Verification provides assurance that the XMM fulfils the specified requirements (e.g. the requirements set by the national regulations), and individual calibration coefficients with associated measurement uncertainties are typically not provided to the user.

In many countries, national regulations exist mandating either calibration or verification (Komatina et al., 2025), and the users should make sure that all the relevant regulations are followed. Where no such regulations exist, the choice between the calibration and verification depends on the user needs and the uncertainty goals. It is important to note that in most cases the lowest uncertainty goals (e.g. 7 % uncertainty with $k = 2$) can be met only by using dedicated calibration coefficients and controlling the exposure conditions in both the clinic and the calibration laboratory, and having sufficient knowledge about the XMM that is used. Verifications may be sufficient to meet more relaxed uncertainty goals (e.g. 20 %), but even then it is important to make sure that the actual measurement conditions (dose rate, filtration, tube voltage) are within the measurement range of the XMM that is used. Using dosimeters that are compliant with relevant IEC standards (IEC, 2023; IEC, 2024) limits the uncertainty and provides greater confidence in measurement results and greater knowledge about dosimeter performance. Older and discontinued types of XMMs should be used with special care, because their performance may not be in line with current standards and regulations.

Calibration or verification interval is set by national regulations in many countries, and the most common interval is two years (Komatina et al., 2025). IAEA TRS 457 recommends the calibration interval of no more than two years, where national regulations do not exist (IAEA, 2007). Some users may require more frequent calibrations, e.g. if XMMs are used very frequently. Calibration or verification should also be performed if the XMM is suddenly behaving unexpectedly (e.g. unusual readings are observed, which cannot be otherwise explained) or after repair.

XMMs measure several quantities, and in principle, calibration or verification should be performed for all the quantities that are used. However, a European survey has shown that calibration services are not widely available for all quantities (Komatina et al., 2025), and currently IEC standards exist only for air kerma (IEC, 2024) and tube voltage (IEC, 2024).

Calibration certificates provide the information required for the correct application of calibration coefficients. They typically include details on the calibration conditions, radiation quality, reference standards used, metrological traceability, reported uncertainty, and coverage factor. To achieve the lowest measurement uncertainties, it is typically necessary to multiply the indicated value by the appropriate calibration coefficient and, where applicable, any additional correction factors. If correction factors are not explicitly known or applied, the impact of deviations from calibration conditions should at least be reflected in the estimated measurement uncertainty.

A key consideration is the difference between calibration conditions and measurement conditions. Factors such as radiation quality (anode/filter combination, tube voltage, inherent and added filtration), measurement geometry, field size, and environmental conditions may influence the dosimeter response. When these conditions differ from those used during calibration, additional corrections or uncertainty components may be required. Since calibrations are typically performed using standardised radiation qualities, calibration coefficients should be selected that best match the clinical measurement scenario.

If the radiation quality used in the measurement lies between radiation qualities for which calibration coefficients are available, the user should evaluate whether interpolation is valid and how deviations from calibration conditions may affect the dosimeter response. The variation of calibration coefficients across different radiation qualities may be used as an indicator of the energy dependence of the response and can support the estimation of associated uncertainty contributions.

In practice, users should understand the performance characteristics and limitations of their instruments, request calibrations that are representative of their intended clinical use and assess whether differences between calibration and measurement conditions introduce significant additional uncertainty. Proper selection and application of calibration coefficients are critical for achieving reliable, traceable, and defensible measurement results in clinical dosimetry.

10 Recommendations for measurement uncertainty

10.1 Introduction

Measurement does not only consist of a measured value, but also of the uncertainty of this value. Measurement uncertainty describes the accuracy and the precision of the result in total. In other words, it includes every source of error and their effect on the result. The better the performance of the equipment and the smaller the variation of the measurement setup is, the smaller the uncertainty is. In addition, if the variations of the measurement setup can be reduced, the uncertainty will be smaller likewise. The uncertainty budget quantifies and accounts for all sources of uncertainty in the measurement process.

First, we give uncertainty estimates for conventional radiography. We focus on three quantities: air kerma, kVp, and half-value layer. We discuss about other modalities later in this document, and we point out similarities and differences compared to conventional radiography. We specify the recommendations only for dosimeters, hence this document does not cover the use of some other type of instrument.

10.2 Exclusions

For these recommendations, we consider only the uncertainties related to the dosimeter and its performance itself. This means we do not estimate uncertainties originating from the whole setup of the measurement, only the angulation and the rotation of the dosimeter itself. If the user of the dosimeter can make the setup accurate repeatedly, additional uncertainty will be small. It can be estimated by conducting complimentary measurements near the correct spot or by using models like inverse-square law, depending on the level of accuracy needed.

Furthermore, we do not make assessments of uncertainties due to possible suboptimal performance of an X-ray device. The functionality of an X-ray device must be checked regularly with quality control measures and through maintenance.

Although we do not include these two aspects in the recommendations, the effects of them have to be taken into account and assessed locally. We cannot give certain values of uncertainty that would cover all the situations, unless the values are relatively large and thus unpractical.

10.3 Uncertainty estimates for general radiography

The following sections cover uncertainty estimates for air kerma, kVp and HVL measurements using dosimeters within general radiography. It is assumed that measurement conditions meet the recommended minimum rated ranges as stated in TraMeXI Deliverable 4 (TraMeXI, 2026), which gives recommendations for updating the minimum rated ranges in IEC 61674 (IEC, 2024).

10.3.1 Air kerma measurements

The uncertainty budget for air kerma measurements is shown in Table 10.1. It is based on IEC 61674 (IEC, 2024), which assumes the use of ionization chambers. Some values are slightly changed according to the measurements carried out during the TraMeXI project. With the measurements, we gathered more information about the variances of dosimeter performance and influencing quantities. If XMMs are used, the budget may differ a bit.

Table 10.1. The uncertainty budget for air kerma measurements, divided into components.

Component	Quantity: Air kerma		
	Relative standard uncertainty (\pm %)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Calibration coefficient	2,89	1,00	0,50
Linearity	1,15	0,58	0,29
Repeatability	0,58	0,58	0,12
Resolution of reading	0,29	0,29	0,12
Stabilization time	1,15	0,29	0,00
Long term stability	1,15	0,29	0,12
Accumulated dose stability	0,58	0,58	0,29
Radiation quality	2,89	0,87	0,29
Air kerma rate	1,15	0,58	0,29
Incidence of radiation	1,15	0,58	0,00
Rotation	0,29	0,29	0,17
Operating voltage	1,15	1,15	0,58
Air pressure	1,15	0,58	0,58
Temperature and humidity	1,73	0,58	0,17
Electromagnetic compatibility	2,89	2,89	1,15
Field size	1,73	1,73	1,15
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)	6,4	4,1	2,0
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 2$)	12,8	8,3	4,0

Unless stated otherwise, Cases 1, 2 and 3 correspond to Scenarios 1, 2 and 3 in IAEA TRS-457 Section 8.3.2, respectively (IAEA, 2007). In other words, Case 1 is the minimum level of performance, where the user of the dosimeter performs measurements and does not apply any further quality assurance tests to reduce the uncertainty. For air density correction, the use of normal air pressure and temperature at the measurement location is adequate, if the dosimeter does not make the correction automatically. The dosimeter is a field class dosimeter.

In Case 2, a reference class dosimeter is used. This means that the meter's performance surpasses the requirements of IEC 61674. The dosimeter is calibrated by an SSDL, and thus the overall uncertainty can be reduced notably. Now, the air density correction must be made with actual air pressure and temperature during measurement. Apart from that, Cases 1 and 2 correspond to each other.

If the measurement conditions and setup are controlled well and the effects of relevant influence quantities are considered, the measurement uncertainty can be reduced even more. This is done in Case 3. For example, if the calibration certificate does not have a calibration coefficient for a certain radiation quality, an estimate may be calculated through interpolation. Quality control measurements are used to investigate the effects of influence quantities on the uncertainty. As in Case 2, a reference class dosimeter is used, and the air density correction is made appropriately.

As stated in Deliverable 4, we introduce a new influencing quantity, rotation of a dosimeter. The rotation is done in the measurement plane, around the line from the focus of the X-ray device to the reference point of the dosimeter. The effect of the rotation on the uncertainty is relatively small, but noticeable.

Of all the influencing quantities, the uncertainty originating from electromagnetic fields is the most significant one. Unfortunately, within the scope of TraMeXI project, we could not investigate this in order to decrease its effect on combined uncertainty. We hope that this will be considered in the future so that the overall uncertainty could be reduced.

As mentioned earlier, the impact of several components can be decreased by conducting additional measurements or restricting variations of influencing quantities. For instance, the effect of temperature and humidity may easily be reduced by examining the effects on air kerma results over a longer period of time, or by maintaining the measurement conditions within stricter limits than minimum rated ranges.

When considering XMMs, some variations can be significantly smaller than with ICs. For example, the effects of air pressure or temperature and humidity may be minor or even negligible. This is due to the structure and the functionality of XMMs.

10.3.2 Tube voltage measurements

For kVp measurements, the basis is IEC 61676 (IEC, 2023). Measurements are assumed to be performed with an XMM, which can calculate kVp from air kerma related measurements. If the beam is attenuated, it is more difficult to measure accurately. XMMs are more precise with (intrinsic) aluminium filters. When copper is added, it is crucial that kVp does not change. When changes in kVp indication are observed, they have to be either corrected or considered in the uncertainty budget

The uncertainty assessment for kVp measurements is presented in Table 10.10.2. As with air kerma, Cases 1, 2 and 3 represent Scenarios 1, 2 and 3 in TRS-457, respectively (IAEA, 2007). Rotation is included as a new component with kVp, too.

The combined standard uncertainty is clearly smaller for kVp than for air kerma. There are several different influencing quantities in comparison to components in Table 10.1, and their variations are smaller. In addition, uncertainties related to the calibration coefficient are much smaller. There is not any specific influencing quantity which contributes heavily to the overall uncertainty.

There are two uncertainties related to field size in Tables 10.2 and 10.4. When using field sizes within the rated range of the dosimeter, the uncertainty is very small, and the component for the large field size can be neglected. If measurements are done outside the rated range, the uncertainty is also larger, and both components must be taken into account.

As it was stated earlier, this document does not include components related to the measurement setup or the X-ray device itself. Thus, for Tables 10.2 and 10.4, we excluded detector-focal distance and tube aging, which were included in IEC 61676. Typical values for their uncertainties are in Table 10.3.

Table 10.2. The uncertainty budget for kVp measurements with XMMs, divided into components.

Component	Quantity: kVp		
	Relative standard uncertainty (\pm %)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Calibration coefficient	0,58	0,30	0,10
Voltage waveform and frequency	1,15	0,58	0,29
Anode angle	0,29	0,29	0,29
Filtration	0,87	0,87	0,43
Dose rate	0,29	0,29	0,12
Irradiation time	0,29	0,12	0,12
Field size: rated range	0,29	0,29	0,29
Field size: large	1,15	0,58	0,58
Angle of incidence	0,29	0,29	0,00
Rotation	0,29	0,29	0,17
Temperature and humidity	0,58	0,58	0,00
Power supply	0,29	0,29	0,29
Electromagnetic compatibility	0,58	0,58	0,29
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)	2,2	1,6	1,0
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 2$)	4,5	3,3	2,0

Table 10.3. Uncertainty components mentioned in IEC 61676 and left out in Table 10.2.

Component	Relative standard uncertainty (\pm %)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Detector-focal distance	0,29	0,29	0,12
Tube aging	1,15	1,15	0,58

10.3.3 Half-value layer measurements

HVL can be determined basically with three different methods: 1) straight with an XMM from an air kerma measurement, just like kVp, 2) by using linear regression to data points from attenuation measurements with an IC and aluminum filters, or 3) by using a spectrometer to measure the spectrum which is then used to calculate the HVL. Because the methods are different, they require separate uncertainty analysis. As spectrometers are rarely used in clinical practice, we omit the last method. Further information on this topic can be found in (Šolc et al., 2025a; Šolc et al., 2025b)

There are no standards which give estimates for HVL measurement uncertainty. For XMMs, we chose IEC 61676 (IEC, 2023) as the basis for HVL measurement uncertainty, because HVL measurements resemble kVp measurements with them. Uncertainty estimates for HVL measurements with XMMs are given in Table 10.4. It

is crucial not to use additional filters with XMMs, because it would distort the results. The components left out are listed in Table 10.3, as was done with kVp.

If HVL is measured with an IC and aluminum filters, it is not possible to form such a simple uncertainty budget, because the use of linear regression is necessary. Different variations related to measuring air kerma and filter properties have to be taken into account, and possible correlations should be checked, too. Uncertainties may vary greatly with different radiation qualities. If everything is done properly, the combined standard uncertainty can be around 2.0 % ($k = 2$). In order to achieve this, the following sources of uncertainty must be controlled well: the properties of the IC (e.g. energy dependence, temperature and air density corrections), filter thickness (uniformity and purity) and the use of linear regression for HVL value estimation.

Table 10.4. The uncertainty budget for HVL measurements with XMMs, divided into components.

Quantity: HVL			
Component	Relative standard uncertainty (\pm %)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Calibration coefficient	2,89	1,50	1,00
Voltage waveform and frequency	1,15	0,58	0,29
Anode angle	0,29	0,29	0,29
Filtration	0,87	0,87	0,43
Dose rate	0,29	0,29	0,12
Irradiation time	0,29	0,12	0,12
Field size: rated range	0,29	0,29	0,29
Field size: large	1,15	0,58	0,58
Angle of incidence	0,29	0,29	0,00
Rotation	0,29	0,29	0,17
Temperature and humidity	0,58	0,58	0,00
Power supply	0,29	0,29	0,29
Electromagnetic compatibility	0,58	0,58	0,29
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)	3,6	2,2	1,4
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 2$)	7,2	4,4	2,8

10.4 Other modalities

The rest of the document deals with possible differences between conventional radiography and other imaging modalities which are within the scope of the TraMeXI project. The measurement setups may differ greatly between different modalities, which the user of the dosimeter has to consider while assessing measurement uncertainties. For example, limited space may restrict the setup resulting in larger uncertainties.

10.4.1 Fluoroscopy

Fluoroscopic X-ray devices have similarities compared to the ones used in general radiography. For example, the tube voltage range is almost identical. Both usually have additional copper filtration, too, although the filtration is often thicker in fluoroscopy.

With fluoroscopy, X-ray pulses are shorter, because the user records multiple frames per second. As the pulses are shorter, their edges may not be as sharp as with longer pulses of general radiography. Also air kerma rates are usually higher. Therefore, it is possible that there are small differences in the uncertainty budget of fluoroscopy versus general radiography. Despite that, we conclude that these differences are so small that it is completely adequate to use the same uncertainties as in Tables 10.1, 10.2 and 10.4.

10.4.2 Dental imaging

Dental imaging devices have typically a bit narrower kVp range compared to general radiography. Their additional filtration is usually thinner, too, or they do not even have any copper filters. Pulse widths are somewhat the same, although there can be much longer pulses with extraoral imaging. This means that dental imaging can be considered as a part of general radiography. That is why the uncertainties in Tables 10.1, 10.2 and 10.4 are also valid with dental imaging.

The user of the dosimeter has to pay attention to the fact that the sensor may not be fully exposed, particularly with extraoral devices and panoramic imaging. This can inflict unreliable results. The use of stationary irradiation is recommended, if possible. Measurement uncertainty can be reduced further by considering also the orientation of the field and the position of the maximum intensity.

10.4.3 Mammography

Mammography differs the most from general radiography. Anode and filter materials vary greatly and kVp range starts from very low and ends about where the general radiography's range begins. This means that radiation qualities are much softer. Air kerma rates are smaller, the X-ray tube is tilted, and the Heel effect is strong. Furthermore, the placement of the dosimeter is specific. Also, the use of compression paddle is distinct to mammography, and it changes photon spectra and scatter conditions.

If the dosimeter is specifically meant for mammography measurements, it does not have to cover the minimum rated ranges fully, but it must cover at least all the radiation qualities listed in Section 3.4 in Deliverable 4 (TraMeXI, 2026). Because of this, the variation related to radiation quality effects can be reduced from 1.5 % to 1.0 %. Consequently, the respective uncertainty in Case 2 of Table 10.1 can be reduced from 0.87 % to 0.58 %. This results in combined standard uncertainty of 9.0 % ($k = 2$), a value 0.1 % smaller than the original.

Despite the differences, we recommend using the same uncertainties for mammography as in Tables 10.1, 10.2 and 10.4 except for radiation quality as stated earlier. If the setup of the dosimeter is done carefully, the effect of scattered radiation will not differ greatly from general radiography, especially with XMMs as they have shielding against scattered photons.

11 References

BIPM. Key comparison database, www.bipm.org/kcdb, accessed on 14.04.2026.

Costa de Castro M, Toroi P, Kortensniemi M, Lindholm C, Pinto M, Rinaldi L, et al. Impact of the measurement conditions and compression paddle on mammography dosimeter response. *Phys Med* 2024;123:103405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2024.103405>.

Hourdakis CJ, Csete I, Daures J, Jarvinen H, Mihailescu L-C, Sochor V, Novak L, Pedersen M, Kosunen A, Toroi P, Denoziere M, Büermann L, Megzifene A, Einarsson G, Ferrari P, dePooter J, Bjerke H, Brodecki M, Cardoso J, Bercea S, Ciraj-Bjelac O, Compel J, Glavič-Cindro D, Ginjaume M, Persson L, Grindborg J-E. Comparison of air kerma area product and air kerma meter calibrations for X-ray radiation qualities used in diagnostic radiology, *Metrologia* 2015;52(1A): 06024, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0026-1394/52/1A/06024>

IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency). Dosimetry in diagnostic radiology: An international code of practice, Technical report series no. 457. Vienna International Atomic Energy Agency; 2007

IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency). Implementation of the International Code of Practice on Dosimetry in Diagnostic Radiology (TRS 457): Review of Test Results, IAEA human health report no. 4. Vienna International Atomic Energy Agency; 2011

IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency). IAEA-TECDOC-1585, Measurement Uncertainty, A Practical Guide for Secondary Standards Dosimetry Laboratories, 2008

ICRU. Physical aspects of Irradiation: Recommendations of the International Commission on Radiological Units and Measurements (ICRU), Report 10b, Handbook 85, 1962.

ICRU. Patient dosimetry for X rays used in medical imaging. International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements (ICRU), Report 74, *J ICRU* 2005;5(2):1–113.

IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission). Medical electrical equipment - Dosimetric instruments used for non-invasive measurement of X-ray tube voltage in diagnostic radiology (IEC 61676:2023).

IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission). Medical electrical equipment - Dosimeters with ionization chambers and/or semiconductor detectors as used in X-ray diagnostic imaging (IEC 61674:2024).

IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission). Medical diagnostic X-ray equipment - Radiation conditions for use in the determination of characteristics. IEC 61267. Geneva: IEC, 2025.

ISO (International Organization for Standardization). X and gamma reference radiation for calibrating dosimeters and doserate meters and for determining their response as a function of photon energy - Part 4: Calibration of area and personal dosimeters in low energy X reference radiation fields. Annex I. ISO 4037-4:2019. Geneva: ISO, 2019.

JCGM (The Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology). Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), 2008

Kojić A, Kržanović N, Živanović M, Toroi P, Bakrač L, Božović P, et al. Influence of anode/filtration setup on X-ray multimeter energy response in mammography applications. *Radiat Meas* 2024;174:107135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2024.107135>.

Kojic A, Toroi P, Kržanović N, Šolc J, Vitikainen A-M, Kortensniemi M, et al. Influence of radiation field size on HVL measurements in mammography. Unpublished manuscript, submitted to *Physica Medica* in January 2026.

Kržanović N, Blideanu V, Ciraj-Bjelac O, Plagnard J, Schoonjans W, Zivanovic M, et al. Performance testing of dosimeters used in interventional radiology: Results from the VERIDIC project. *Radiat Meas* 2021;141:106515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106515>.

Krzanovic N, Toroi P, Komatina I, Jansen B, Boziari A, Caldeira M, et al. 2026 X-ray imaging dosimeter performance in standard and non-standard radiography radiation fields in terms of air kerma. *Phys Med* 2026;141:105687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2025.105687>.

Kržanović N, Toroi P, Stojanovic I, Costa de Castro MC, Stojanovića I, Boziari A, et al. Performance of X-ray multimeters for measurement of voltage-related quantities, half-value layer, total filtration and exposure time in X-ray imaging. Unpublished manuscript, 2026.

Rinaldi L, Ciccotelli A, Silvestri C, Petrucci A, Cappadozzi G, Toma S, et al. Implementation of the ISO 4037:2019 standard using voltage dividers and X-ray spectrometry. Unpublished manuscript in-press, accepted to Radiation Protection Dosimetry, 2026

Salomon E, Homolka P, Csete I, Toroi P. Performance of semiconductors dosimeters with a range of radiation qualities used for mammography: a calibration laboratory study. *Med Phys* 2020;47(3):1372–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.14005>.

Salomon E, Homolka P, Csete I, Toroi P. Energy dependence of the response of X-ray multimeter for radiation qualities in mammography. *Sci Rep* 2025;15:9857. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-93485-5>.

Sechopoulos I, Dance DR, Boone JM, Bosmans HT, Caballo M, Diazet O, et al. Joint AAPM Task Group 282/EFOMP Working Group Report: Breast dosimetry for standard and contrast-enhanced mammography and breast tomosynthesis. *Med. Phys.* 2024; 51: 712–739. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.16842>.

Šolc J, Šmoldasová J, Štemberková L, Sochor V, Vykydal Z. Improved setup and characterization of cadmium telluride detector for in-beam X-ray spectrometry up to 300 kV at Czech Metrology Institute. *JINST* 2025a;20:P02012. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/20/02/P02012>.

Šolc J, Pojtinger S, Šmoldasová J, Sochor V, Rusňák J. The spectrometric practical voltage: determination of X-ray tube voltage up to 300 kV by in-beam X-ray spectrometry with a cadmium telluride detector. *J Inst.* 2025b Feb;20(02):P02013. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/20/02/P02013> (Open Access)

Šolc J, Borowski M, Ciccotelli A, Cannatà V, Kortetniemi M, Pinto M, et al. Photon fluence spectra from various medical X-ray imaging systems measured using a compact cadmium telluride spectrometer. Unpublished manuscript, to be submitted to JINST, 2026.

Stasko JT, Culberson WS. X-ray multimeter performance under calibration laboratory conditions. *Med Phys* 2025;52(9):e18106. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.18106>.

Tietäväinen A, Toroi P, Jansen B, Klauenberg K, Saroka S, Šolc J, et al. Calibration of X-ray multimeters for half-value layer: measurement methods and uncertainty evaluation. Unpublished manuscript.

Toroi P, Valkama V, Kaasalainen T, Kiiskinen N, Kortetniemi M, Pousi P, Šolc J Calibration of X-ray multimeters for radiography. Submitted to *Physica Medica* 2026.

TraMeXI. 22NRM01 TraMeXI Deliverable 4, 2026.